

The graphic features a central orange circle with a white flower-like pattern. This is surrounded by three smaller circles (blue, green, and green) connected by curved lines. The entire graphic is set against a background of large, semi-transparent circles in light blue, light green, and light orange, with a magnifying glass icon in the top right.

ODECO

Towards a sustainable Open Data ECOsystem

D6.6 Final Conference

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.
The opinions expressed in this document reflect only the author's view and in no way reflect the European Commission's opinions. The European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Project Acronym	ODECO
Project Title	Towards a sustainable Open Data ECOsystem
Grant Agreement No.	955569
Start date of Project	01-10-2021
Duration of the Project	48 months
Deliverable Number	D6.6
Deliverable Title	Final Conference
Dissemination Level	Public
Deliverable Leader	Farosnet Single Member S.A.
Submission Date	03-07-2025
Author	Manolis Ktistakis (Farosnet)
Co-author(s)	An. Furlis, G. Papageorgiou (Farosnet)

Document history

Version #	Date	Description (Section, page number)	Author & Organisation
V0.1	26-06-2025	First draft	Manolis Ktistakis (Farosnet), Antonis Furlis (Farosnet), Georgios. Papageorgiou (Farosnet)
V0.1a	27-06-2025	Review	Charalampos (Harris) Alexopoulos (UAEGEAN) Danitsja van Heusden (TU Delft)
V0.2	27-06-2025	Second draft. Processed feedback obtained from the peer review process.	Manolis Ktistakis (Farosnet), Antonis Furlis (Farosnet), Georgios. Papageorgiou (Farosnet)
V0.2a	01-07-2025	Review	Danitsja van Heusden (TU Delft)
V0.3	02-07-2025	Final report	Manolis Ktistakis (Farosnet), Georgios. Papageorgiou (Farosnet)
V1.0	03-07-2025	Approval	Danitsja van Heusden (TU Delft)

Table of Contents

Abbreviations	5
1 Introduction.....	6
1.1 Final Conference Objectives.....	6
1.2 Setup of the program.....	6
1.3 Location.....	7
1.4 Organization and involvement of the ESRs	9
1.5 Public engagement, social impact and dissemination	9
1.5.1 Public Engagement and Social impact.....	9
1.5.2 Dissemination.....	10
2 Day 1	12
2.1 Objectives, activities, assignments, and program	12
2.2 Evaluation of Day 1.....	14
3 Day 2.....	16
3.1 Objectives, activities, assignments, and program	16
3.2 Evaluation of Day 2.....	19
4 Day 3	22
4.1 Objectives, activities, assignments, and program	22
4.2 Evaluation of Day 3.....	23
5 Participation and attendance	25
5.1 Overall.....	25
5.2 Day 1	25
5.3 Day 2	25
5.4 Day 3	25
Annex 1 - List of attendees.....	26
Annex 2 – Presentations	31
Annex 3 – Posters.....	32
Annex 4 – Practical recommendations.....	33

List of figures

Figure 1: Mapped areas selected around the Athens BC hotel.....	8
Figure 2: Olympia Meeting Room – Stratos Vassilikos Hotel.	8
Figure 3: Picture from the Final Conference page on the ODECO site.....	11
Figure 4: Pictures from the introduction and mapping.....	13
Figure 5: Pictures from the Café Avissinia dinner	15
Figure 6: Pictures from the Presentations of ESRs.....	18
Figure 7: Pictures from round table discussions	21
Figure 8: Pictures from Speakers.....	24

List of tables

Table 1: List of invited Organisations.....	10
Table 2: Program Day 1	14
Table 3: Program Day 2.....	18
Table 4: Program Day 3.....	22

Abbreviations

D	Deliverable
ESR	Early-Stage Researcher
ODECO	Open Data ECOsystem
NGOs	Non-Governmental Organisations

Nr	Partner	Partner short name	Country
Beneficiary			
1	Technische Universiteit Delft	TU Delft	Netherlands
2	Katholieke Universiteit Leuven	KUL	Belgium
3	Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique	CNRS	France
4	Universidad de Zaragoza	UNIZAR	Spain
5	Panepistimio Aigaiou	UAEGEAN	Greece
6	Aalborg Universitet	AAU	Denmark
7	Università degli Studi di Camerino	UNICAM	Italy
8	Farosnet S.A.	FAROSNET S.A.	Greece
Partner organisations			
1	7eData	7EDATA	Spain
2	Digitaal Vlaanderen	DV	Belgium
3	City of Copenhagen	COP	Denmark
4	City of Rotterdam	RDAM	Netherlands
5	CoC Playful Minds	CoC	Denmark
6	Derilinx	DERI	Ireland
7	ESRI	ESRI	Netherlands
8	Maggioli S.p.A	MAG	Italy
9	National Centre of Geographic Information	CNIG	Spain
10	Open Knowledge Belgium	OKB	Belgium
11	SWECO	SWECO	Netherlands
12	The government lab	GLAB	United States of America
13	Agency for Data Supply and Infrastructure	ADSI	Denmark
14	GFOSS Open Technologies Alliance	GFOSS	Greece
15	Inno3 Consulting	IC	France
16	Regione Marche	RM	Italy
17	Open Data Institute	OCI	United Kingdom
18	Swedish National Archives	SwNA	Sweden

1 Introduction

1.1 Final Conference Objectives

The ODECO Final Conference marks the culmination of a 4-year EU funded Horizon 2020 Marie Skłodowska-Curie Innovative Training Network initiative. It was organized by Farosnet S.A. with the assistance of the Delft University of Technology and the University of Aegean. ODECO beneficiaries agreed in organizing the conference in two different locations in the city of Athens, Greece in the 3-day period between May 14th-16th, 2025.

In defining the program of the week, the following relevant objectives were considered:

1. The best possible presentation of the results of the ODECO project and its Early-Stage Researchers (ESRs) to three separate groups, namely:
 - a. the general public;
 - b. the scientific community and;
 - c. professionals.
2. The feedback that was received from the beneficiaries and especially the ESRs in relation to what they expected to achieve out of the event.
3. The overall involvement of the ESRs in the organization of the different aspects and days of the final conference.
4. The maximization of public engagement, attendance and social impact of the activities, especially in the day that regarded the general public.
5. Prioritization of the involvement of external actors and ODECO partners to permit the exchange of ideas with people not involved in the ODECO project, but with experience either in Open Data or in specific aspects of the organized activities.
6. The increase of public awareness for the ODECO project through the creation and dissemination of content through the social media of ODECO.
7. A social event was included in the planning to enable the ESRs and their supervisors to enjoy their final major gathering as a celebration of their common efforts to advance Open Data research leading to the creation of an Open Data Ecosystem.

In the following sections the details of the Final Conference and its results are examined.

1.2 Setup of the program

The program was divided in 3 different days:

1. The first day was dedicated to the involvement of the general public in the Final Conference. This was done through the selection of a mapping event that would increase the social impact of ODECO and also spread awareness about open data and the role they can play in the wider community of people, especially to people that are not involved in open data in their daily life. More specifically, the organization committee along with the ODECO ESRs, after examining various different ideas, decided that the best approach to engaging the wider public in an open data related activity and achieving social impact was mapping an area around the ancient site of the acropolis of Athens. This is an area that receives hundreds of thousands of visitors and tourists each year. The idea that prevailed was to examine how accessible it is for people with disabilities and map the data on Open Street Maps (i.e. an open repository), so it is freely accessible for all future visitors that have interest in such data.
2. The second day of the Final Conference, which was a full day, was devoted entirely to the ESRs and the presentation of their research to the scientific community. The presentations were structured in 3 major thematic groups: "Open data ecosystems beyond open government data", "Emerging technologies for open data" and "Power dynamics in the generation, use and regulation of open data". After the presentations of the ESRs comprising each thematic group, panel discussions were organized, where the main research proposals of each ESRs

were further discussed with the participation of the members of the audience. These discussions were carried out first into five smaller “break away” groups (including a hybrid group for those attending through the internet) and then the main points discussed by each “break away” group were presented to the wider audience.

The aim of this process was:

- a) To further embed the key take aways of the research of each ESR to the academic community and the attendees.
 - b) To “test” and enrich them through discussions with the audience. In the end, our intention was to highlight the diverse aspects into the open data world that each ERS “brought to the table” through the lens of his/her individual doctoral research.
 - c) To combine them in a multi-disciplinary academic approach addressing current and future challenges in the creation of a user driven, circular and inclusive Open Data Ecosystem.
3. The third day of the Final Conference of ODECO was dedicated to professionals and experts (both from the government and the private sector) working daily with open data mainly in Greece, but also in EU level. They presented the work they do to the audience and shared their experience with open data, their plans and expected developments in this field and accepted questions from our ESRs, ODECO professors and other attendees. Through engaging with government representatives, industrial experts, practitioners in the field and policy makers, participants reflected on the ODECO project’s outcomes and discussed future strategies for advancing open data ecosystems. This session offered valuable insights into evolving open data governance models and their implications for public policy and business practices. Finally, issues related to the job market in general and in particular to open data scientists were discussed with an industry expert.

1.3 Location

Due to the different themes of the 3 days of the conference, two different venues were elected. More specifically, as venue for the 1st day of the conference the Coco-mat Athens BC hotel (located on Falirou 5, Athens 117 42) was elected, since it was situated in the ideal location for the activities related to the mapping event around the Acropolis of Athens, see Figure 1, as it is literally located next to the museum of Acropolis and in the epicentre of the area the mapping event focused on. The venue was also accessible for people with disabilities (that were using for example wheelchairs or walking canes etc), which was important, as the 1st day workshop was focused on this specific group of people.

The convenient location of the Coco-mat Athens BC Hotel allowed the five different teams that were designated to carry out the mapping of the five areas next to the Acropolis site, to commute in a short amount of time between the hotel and the areas that they were covering and then back to the hotel. This, in turn, allowed enough time to first brief everyone on what needed to be done and how to use the materials and tools provided for doing the mapping and what the aims of the mapping exercise were. Then, when the “on the spot” mapping exercise was concluded, everybody had time to reconvene back at the hotel and discuss their experiences.

Figure 1: Mapped areas selected around the Athens BC hotel.

The 2nd and 3rd day of the Final Conference were carried out in the Airotel Stavros Vassilikos Hotel (114 Michalakopoulou St., 11527 Athens). The location was convenient, near the centre of Athens, but not in the city centre that can be problematic to access from time to time (in case there are demonstrations etc).

The Stratos Vassilikos Hotel is located close to the “Megaro Mousikis” metro station and other public transportation. The Olympia Meeting room, see Figure 2, that was used for the purposes of the ODECO Final conference can accommodate up to 110 people and offered all the necessary amenities that were required for the conference (WIFI - Air conditioning - Microphone - Display/LCD/Video projection capabilities).

Figure 2: Olympia Meeting Room – Stratos Vassilikos Hotel.

As the organization committee wanted to attract as many attendees as possible, it elected to organize the 2nd and 3rd day not only physically, but to also allow anyone that wanted to attend the ODECO final conference online hybrid attendance (by using MS Teams). Therefore, hybrid meeting capabilities were offered for the Final Conference through engaging a specialized company that offered the necessary audio-visual equipment.

1.4 Organization and involvement of the ESRs

Since the Final Conference of ODECO was closely related to the doctoral research that the 15 ESRs of the program had undertaken, it was self-explanatory that the ESRs would also be hugely involved in the preparation and execution of the Final Conference itself, which in turn would be structured in a way that would showcase their work and achievements.

In fact, in the preparatory meetings that took place in advance of the Conference, the ESRs requested that they be on the “spotlight” i.e. that the focus of the conference was on them. Based on these instructions the schedule itself was arranged in such a manner that the central (2nd) day of the conference, which was the longest of the conference days, was devoted exclusively to the ESRs to give them ample time to present their research and proposals for the creation of a user driven, circular and inclusive Open Data Ecosystem to the scientific community.

In order to help achieve this goal, besides their presentations, all the ESRs were also asked to prepare a visual representation of the key findings of their research, which was synthesized in a big banner that was presented in the conference room during the 2nd and 3rd day of the conference (as presented in Annex 3). These posters were also used as the drivers of the discussion between the ESRs and the audience and generally played a pivotal role in the conference organizational process.

Additionally, the ESRs took it upon themselves to be the hosts of the 2nd day, and acted as moderators of the sessions, leaders of the break-away round tables, reporters of the discussed issues in them and originators of questions and discussions points.

The assistance of a select group of ESRs was also paramount in the planning and organization of the public outreach activities of the 1st day of the conference, in organizing first the preparatory workshop for it and then the actual day itself, in explaining to the audience what needed to be done and what was the purpose of the day, in leading the mapping teams and in the end in discussing the findings with the audience.

Finally, the ESRs played a major role in the 3rd day by asking questions and exchanging views with the speakers both officially but also networking with them during the breaks.

1.5 Public engagement, social impact and dissemination

The overall public engagement and social impact of the Final Conference were very important to the organizers and the ESRs. Additionally, steps were taken to increase the dissemination and the legacy of the project with are described below.

1.5.1 Public Engagement and Social impact

Public engagement was sought in various different manners throughout the Final Conference. This was even more evident in relation to the first day of the event that was actually targeted to the public and its involvement in the ODECO project.

The theme of the 1st day itself was elected by the ERSs (after discussions and various suggestions by the organizers). Its focus was on a matter that touches hundreds if not thousands of visitors that are moving around the touristically important area of the Acropolis of Athens. These visitors may be facing significant difficulties if the area, the shops and even public infrastructure does not cater to their needs.

The ESRs that were involved in the organization of the 1st day reached out to numerous Non-Governmental Organisations (NGOs) and other organizations of people with disabilities and moving impairments and requested their presence and participation in the event. The organisation

committee believed that their participation would provide us with their first-hand experiences and add unique perspectives to the discussions. Table 1 provides a list of the NGOs reached out to. A workshop was organized in advance of the first day to request feedback from the NGOs and inquire what they would like to achieve from the event, how to approach the mapping process, and what benefits they could gain from open data, such as improved accessibility, better resource allocation, and enhanced advocacy for their communities.

Table 1: List of invited Organisations

	Type of Organisation	Name	Method of Contact	Website
1	PSO	Municipality of Athens	Phone call	
2	NGO	Inclusive Spaces HE Project	Email	https://inclusivespaces-heproject.eu
3	NGO	National Confederation of Disabled People (ESAMEA)	Email & Phone call	https://www.esamea.gr/el/contact
4	NGO	Cerebral Palsy Greece (CPG)	Email & Phone call	https://www.eps-ath.gr/
5	NGO	Lara Guide-Dog School	Email	https://www.laraguidedschools.gr/
6	NGO	Hellenic Paralympic Committee	Email & Phone call	https://www.paralympic.gr/
7	NGO	IASIS	Email	https://www.iasismed.eu
8	NGO	meallamatia	Email	https://meallamatia.services
9	NGO	Urbana	Email & Phone call	https://urbana.gr
10	NGO	Alzheimer Athens Association	Email & Phone call	https://alzheimerathens.gr/contact/
11	NGO	Σ.Κ.Ε.Π.	Email	https://www.skep.gr
12	NGO	Greek Red Cross	Email & Phone call	http://www.redcross.gr/
13	NGO	OpenStreetMap Greece	Email	
14	NGO	ELEPAP	Email & Phone call	elepap.gr
15	NGO	Child and Adolescent's Center	Email & Phone call	https://kpechios.org/
16	NGO	PLOES	Email & Phone call	https://ploes.org.gr/

Finally, as part of the 2nd day of the conference ESR Ramya Chandrasekhar presented the work she compiled with Prof. Mélanie Dulong de Rosnay (on the basis of the work done by all ODECO ERSs) entitled "Recommendations for Sustainable Open Data Ecosystems," as a general guideline that all open data ecosystems should abide to in order to be financially, socially and ecologically sustainable, equitable, and to empower all stakeholders.

1.5.2 Dissemination

To promote the Final Conference, a special section was created on the [ODECO website](#). This section hosted the invitation and the full program for the Final Conference, providing information on venues, the daily schedule, and a direct registration link. See Figure 3.

ODECO Final Conference

Figure 3: Picture from the Final Conference page on the ODECO site

The activities and organization of the Final Conference were advertised on the ODECO LinkedIn account, where all the ESRs and supervisors are active, with an aim to disseminate this information to their networks, so as to achieve maximum impact and dissemination in the academic and professional community.

To ensure broad participation, invitations to the conference were sent to 73 university departments throughout Greece. This outreach aimed to engage their staff and students, significantly expanding ODECO's reach within the academic community and attracting individuals who could attend physically. Furthermore, invitations were distributed to the program's facilitators and partners, asking them to share the opportunity within their professional networks and with other relevant partners.

Finally, in order for Farosnet S.A. to assist in the dissemination efforts, it decided to utilize its internal resources and experience as an active branch of an international news portal (Huffpost). Specifically, it decided to arrange that a professional videographer would attend the 2nd and 3rd day of the conference to ask the ESRs and their supervising professors to talk about their experience with ODECO and about the final conference itself. Thereafter through a proper editing of the footage it would prepare a video that could be used and in the dissemination effort of the ODECO project. The link to this video from the YouTube channel of ODECO can be found [here](#).

2 Day 1

2.1 Objectives, activities, assignments, and program

The aim of the first day of the conference was to incorporate social groups of people with disabilities and relevant NGOs in a hands-on experience and mix them together with the ODECO ESRs, having in mind two separate objectives:

- a) To demonstrate the value of open data to these groups and NGOs and give them tools that could provide solutions to various problems they encounter in daily life. This would also highlight the power of open data for a more equal and inclusive society.
- b) To understand the different perspectives and needs that these groups of people have, which cannot be comprehended without a hands-on experience and interaction with them. This would help ESRs understand that even academic level efforts to interpret situations and problems is always impaired through the researcher's lens of biases that cannot be overcome without these types of workshops that include first hand interaction with user groups that are the subject of the research. Then our researchers could also to apply this experience in future research endeavours.

The first day of the Final Conference started with an opening speech by the organizers at 13:00h at the Coco-Mat Hotel, warmly welcoming all attendees, including ESRs, supervisors, invited NGO representatives, and other participants. The activities included the formal introduction of the members of ODECO and the participants from the NGOs so they could establish a connection with each other, as they would later work together. This was promptly followed by ESR Héctor Ochoa Ortiz's presenting the main activity that would take place, the areas to be mapped around the Museum of the Acropolis with an explanation about the methodology and the tools that were to be used.

Following those introductory speeches, participants and ESRs were divided in groups that were designated to different preselected parts of the area and the main event of mapping took place from 13:30h – 15:30h. Some pictures from these activities can be found below in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Pictures from the introduction and mapping

Upon their return to the hotel, from 15:30h – 16:00h, ESRs Silvia Cazacu-Bucica and Caterina Santoro facilitated a crucial discussion and reflection session. They presented the issues encountered during the mapping exercise and led a broader discussion on the subject. The day's official program concluded with a closure and networking session from 16:00h – 17:00h where the ODECO members had the opportunity to exchange information and expand their professional network, especially with the NGO representatives, fostering connections for future collaborations.

Finally, after the 1st day conference events were concluded, the ODECO members had two hours to walk around the archaeological sites, and then they met for dinner at Café Avissinia. The detailed program of the 1st day can be found below in Table 2.

Table 2: Program Day 1

Time	Activity
13:00 – 13:30	Welcome & Introduction to the mapping exercise in the Coco-Mat hotel.
13:30 – 15:30	Mapping session in the Athens Acropolis area
15:30 – 16:00	Discussion & Reflection & Conclusions
16:00 – 17:00	Closure & Networking
19:00 – 22:00	Social event: Dinner at “Café Avissinia” restaurant

2.2 Evaluation of Day 1

- The first day was very successful and satisfied the attendees and the ESRs, who expressed their satisfaction about the experience in the discussions that took place after the mapping event.
- All participants admitted that it was extremely important that actual individuals with mobility disabilities participated in the mapping exercise, as they offered their unique perspectives and helped the other participants (and the ESRs) to see the hurdles they are facing and the priorities they have through their own eyes. Everybody admitted that, besides their best efforts to examine this subject, if the individuals with mobility disabilities had not participated, they would have missed a lot of things.
- The ODECO members were surprised how many everyday obstacles they hadn't noticed, highlighting just how challenging life can be for people with mobility impediments.
- They also noted significant gaps in the existing mapping data; several parts of one of the city's most popular areas were not mapped properly, and crucially, didn't provide useful information important for these sensitive groups.
- The NGO representatives showed keen interest in having access to the results of the workshop, highlighting the practical implications of the workshop and the impact that can have in government policies.
- The valuable notes and data gathered from the workshop will be used by the ESRs to conduct further academic research and to publish their findings. These outcomes will be presented both as academic publications and as white papers, specifically tailored for interested stakeholders like the NGOs and the Municipality of Athens.
- Finally, the dinner at the Cafe Avissia restaurant proved to be a very nice and relaxing experience for all ESRs and supervisors, who shared a last united dinner under the view of the Parthenon. Pictures from the dinner can be found on Figure 5 below.

Figure 5: Pictures from the Café Avissinia dinner

3 Day 2

3.1 Objectives, activities, assignments, and program

The second day of the conference was dedicated to the ESRs and the presentation of their academic research.

The main objective was to provide the ESRs an opportunity to present all together the work they did during their time in the ODECO project to a wider audience. Moreover, the conference was not only limited to presentations and Q&A sessions as most academic conferences. The ESRs were split into three groups based on the domain of their research, namely "Open data ecosystems beyond open government data", "Emerging technologies for open data" and "Power dynamics in the generation, use and regulation of open data". Then, when the ESRs of each group presented their work, the attendees were split into 5 tables where they had the opportunity to collect feedback and discuss their research proposal of the ESRs with them and their supervisors of ODECO. Then, one ESR from each group that was keeping notes, presented the discussion outcomes to the whole room during a reflection session where all the participants of the conference could participate.

After the welcome and the registration of the attendees, the day opened at 9:20h with a welcome remark by Prof. Bastiaan van Loenen, the scientific coordinator of the ODECO project, which was followed by a speech by Mr. Sakaretsios Stilianos, who is the president of the board of directors of the Greek land registry (on behalf of the Greek Ministry of Digital Governance). Thereafter from 9.30h to 11:25h the first group of ERS presented their research accomplishments and proposals in the fields of "Open data ecosystems beyond open government data" that was each followed by a table discussion and reflection session in the manner discussed above.

At 11:25h the second group of ESRs presented their research results and proposal regarding "Emerging technologies for open data".

At 12:25h, the event broke for one hour for lunch and was resumed with the table discussion and reflection session for the 2nd group. After, on 14:10h the 3rd group of ESR presentations regarding "Power dynamics in the generation, use and regulation of open data". Pictures from the presentations of ERSs can be found below on Figure 6.

Figure 6: Pictures from the Presentations of ESRs

Finally, in section 4 that started at 16:15h, ESR Ramya Chandrasekhar presented the work she compiled with Prof. Mélanie Dulong de Rosnay entitled "Recommendations for Sustainable Open Data Ecosystems," as a final chapter for discussion on the work that was conducted by all the members of the ODECO consortium. A more detailed programme of Day 2 can be found in Table 3 below.

Table 3: Program Day 2

Time	Activity	Speaker
09:00 – 09:20	Registration and Morning Coffee	
09:20 – 09:30	Welcome remarks	Dr. Bastiaan van Loenen, Delft University of Technology
09:30 – 09:45	Open data in government	Sakaretsios Stilianos, President of the BoD of the Greek land registry

Time	Activity	Speaker
09:45 – 10:45	Session 1: Open data ecosystems beyond open government data	- Ashraf Shaharudin (ESR15) - Giorgos Papageorgiou (ESR09) - Héctor Ochoa Ortiz (ESR13) - Mohsan Ali (ESR05) - Liubov Pilshchikova (ESR11)
10:45 – 11:15	Table discussion session 1 accompanied by coffee	
11:15 – 11:25	Reflection Session 1	
11:25 – 12:45	Session 2: Emerging technologies for open data	- Ioanna Maratsi (ESR07) - Dagoberto Herrera (ESR02) - Umair Ahmed (ESR14) - Alejandra Celis Vargas (ESR10) - Abdul Aziz (ESR08)
12:25 – 13:30	Lunch	
13:30 – 14:00	Table discussion session 2 accompanied by coffee	
14:00 – 14:10	Reflection Session 2	
14:10 – 15:10	Session 3: Power dynamics in the generation, use and regulation of open data	- Silvia Cazacu-Bucica (ESR03) - Caterina Santoro (ESR12) - Ramya Chandrasekhar (ESR04) - Malena Lopez Reyes (ESR06)
15:10 – 15:25	Short Break	
15:25 – 15:55	Table discussion session 3 accompanied by coffee	
15:55 – 16:15	Reflection Session 3	
16:15 – 17:35	Session 4: Looking back to plan for the future	
17:35 – 18:00	Closing remarks	

3.2 Evaluation of Day 2

- The ERSs and their supervisors were satisfied with the presentations and the discussions.
- It was obvious to all supervisors, who have monitored the progress of the ERSs throughout the course of the ODECO project, that all ERSs have mastered their respective areas of research and that their presentations and knowledge have evolved significantly during the last years. The presentations of the ERSs can be found in Annex 2.
- The table discussions and reflections were very useful and the proposals of the ERSs played a vital role in shaping the discussions.
- Generally, there was intense interest from the participants and the supervisors in the findings the ERSs presented, not only during the Q&A of each presentation but also at the round table where the ERSs received feedback from the participants and the supervisors.
- ERSs played a big part in the day, which was focused on them and their achievements.
- In the end, the diverse aspects into the open data research that each ERS's research contributed helped attendees and participants form a multi-disciplinary perspective into open data and the challenges of creating open data ecosystems.

Pictures from the presentations of the speakers can be found in Figure 7 below and their presentations have been included in Annex 2.

Figure 7: Pictures from round table discussions

4 Day 3

4.1 Objectives, activities, assignments, and program

The third day of the conference was focused on professionals from both from the government and the private sector. These professionals are working with open data in their daily work mainly in the Greek government, but also in EU and international level. They presented their experience, developments in their field and plans to our audience and accepted questions from our ESRs, ODECO professors and other attendees.

The day started at 9:00h with an opening remark from Prof. Bastiaan Van Loenen and a keynote by Ms. Els Breedstraet from the Open Data Innovation and Outreach Publications Office of the European Union. After that, the day continued with presentations from the Greek Ministry of Digital Governance (Mr. Antonios Stasis), the Municipality of Athens (Mr. Ioannis Fytros), the Cental Bank of Greece (Mr. Spyridon Gardikiotis), the Greek land registry (Dr. Panagiotis Lolonis), the Greek Ministry of Health (Mr. Ioannis Faropoulos) and finally by Mr. Alexandros Fourlis, Senior Vice President & General Manager of Veritone Hire, an international HR and consulting company. Pictures from the presentations of the speakers can be found in Figure 8 below and their presentations have been included in Annex 2.

The day was finalised with networking drinks and interesting discussions between the speakers, the ERSs, the professors and the attendees. A detailed program of the 3rd day can be found on Table 4 below.

Table 4: Program Day 3

Time	Activity	Speaker
09:30 – 09:45	Opening remark	Bastiaan van Loenen, Delft University of Technology
09:45 – 10:15	Keynote	Els Breedstraet, Head of Open Data Innovation and Outreach, Publications Office of the European Union, European Commission
10:15 – 10:35	Open data in government	Ioannis Fytros, Coordinator of Open Government Partnership Initiative, City of Athens
10:35 – 10:55	Open data in government	Antonios Stasis, Director General of Digital Governance
10:55 – 11:15	Coffee Break	
11:15 – 11:30	Open Data in business	Spyridon Gardikiotis, Director, Bank of Greece
11:30 – 12:00	Open Data in the Greek land registry	Dr. Panagiotis Lolonis, Head of the Directorate of Geospatial Information, Hellenic Land Registry
12:00 – 12:30	Open Data in health	Mr. Giannis Faropoulos, Advisor to the Deputy Minister of Health
12:30 – 13:00	Open Data in the workforce	Mr. Alexandros Fourlis, Senior Vice President & General Manager, Veritone Hire
13:00 – 13:30	Networking drinks	

4.2 Evaluation of Day 3

- All presentations were interesting and helped ERSs and participants gain new perspectives into various sectors of Open data on Greek, EU and international level.
- The various guests that presented are distinguished in their fields and honoured ODECO with their presence in our Final Conference.
- The ESRs posed questions, and many interesting discussions ensued especially about the implementation of open data policies in different counties of the EU.
- A key outcome was that not all organisations are progressing with the same speed in innovations regarding open data and there is a gap between government and private sector, as well as between EU directives and their local implementation.
- According to our HR expert, the professional perspectives for open data professionals are very good with high demand in this field of work.
- Due to the extensive and insightful questions from the ESRs during the Q&A sessions, one speaker slot had to be cancelled to make time to accommodate these in-depth discussions about the practical applications of open data.

Figure 8: Pictures from Speakers

5 Participation and attendance

5.1 Overall

The participation in the ODECO Final conference is deemed satisfactory, especially during the 1st day that was dedicated to the General Public. Overall, 106 people were registered and 62 participated in the 3 days of the conference. A List of attendees can be found on Annex 1.

5.2 Day 1

59 people were registered and 41 participated during the 1st day.

5.3 Day 2

95 people were registered and 40 participated during the 2nd day.

5.4 Day 3

105 people were registered and 46 participated during the 3rd day.

Annex 1 - List of attendees

Id	What is your full name?	Which organisation do you represent?	Day 1 P	Day 2 P	Day 2 O	Day 3 P	Day 3 O	Comment
43	Abdul Aziz	Universidad de Zaragoza	No	No	Yes	No	Yes	Day 2 & 3 online
83	AIKATERINI KESKINIDOU	INTERNATIONAL HELLENIC UNIVERSITY	No	No	No-show	No	No-show	
20	Alejandra Celis Vargas	Aalborg University	Yes	Yes	No-show	Yes	No	Day 2 double (P & O)
120	Alexandros Fourlis	Veritone Hire	No	No	No	Yes	No	Speaker
106	ANGELOS IOANNIS KOUROUGENIS	INTERNATIONAL HELLENIC UNIVERSITY	No-show	No	Yes	No-show	Yes	Day 3 double (P & O)
22	Anneke Zuiderwijk	Delft University of Technology (TU Delft)	No	Yes	No	No	No	Day 2 Physical
123	Antonios Stasis	Ministri of Digital Governance	No	No	No	Yes	No	Speaker
48	Antonis Fourlis	FAROSNET / HUFFPOST GREECE	No	Yes	No-show	Yes	No-show	Day 2 & 3 double (P & O)
77	aristolis skamagkis	Aegean Solutions	No-show	No	No-show	No	No-show	
21	Ashraf Shaharudin	TU Delft	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	
90	Aspasia Psarra	International Hellenic University	No-show	No-show	No-show	No-show	No-show	Day 2 & 3 double (P & O)
16	Bastiaan van Loenen	TU Delft	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Speaker
27	Birger Larsen	Aalborg University	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	No	
49	Caterina Santoro	KU Leuven	Yes	Yes	No-show	Yes	No-show	Day 2 & 3 double (P & O)
121	Charalabidis Yannis	UAEGEAN	No	No	No	Yes	No	
87	Charalampos Giannatsis	University of Western Macedonia	No	No	No-show	No	No-show	
98	CHRISTINA LIATSA	Hellenic Statistical Authority	No	No	No-show	No	No-show	
33	Dagoberto José Herrera Murillo	UNIZAR	Yes	Yes	No-show	Yes	No-show	Day 2 & 3 double (P & O)
119	Damian Murla Tuyls	NIRAS	No	No	Yes	No	No	
67	Damianos Andreou	University of the Aegean	No	No	No-show	No	No-show	
2	Danitsja van Heusden-van Winden	TU Delft	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	
24	Davide Di Staso	TU DELFT	No	No	No-show	No	No-show	Day 2 double (P & O)
62	Despina Vlachou	University of Ioannina	No	No	No-show	No-show	No-show	Day 3 double (P & O)
42	DIMITRA TOURLIDA	Iasis NGO	Yes	No	No	No	No	
5	Dimitra Tsakanika	DAEM - City of Athens IT Company	Yes	No	No	No-show	No	
95	Eef Elschot	Gemeente Rotterdam	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	

Id	What is your full name?	Which organisation do you represent?	Day 1 P	Day 2 P	Day 2 O	Day 3 P	Day 3 O	Comment
44	Efthymios Roumpis	National and Kapodistrian University of Athens	No	No	No-show	No	No-show	
80	EFTHYMIOS TZORTZIS	Private interest	Yes	No-show	Yes	No	Yes	
104	ELENI KAZNAFERI	IASIS	Yes	No	No	No	No	
36	Els Breedstraet	Publications Office of the EU	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	No	Speaker
56	Euripidis Loukis	University of Aegean	No	Yes	No	No	No-show	
110	Evangelos Psarras	Bank of Greece	No	No	No	Yes	No	
6	Evelina Faliagka	URBANA	Yes	No	No	No	No	
124	External 1 - Day 1		Yes	No	No	No	No	
125	External 2 - Day 1		Yes	No	No	No	No	
126	External 3 - Day 1		Yes	No	No	No	No	
127	External 4 - Day 1		Yes	No	No	No	No	
128	External 5 - Day 1		Yes	No	No	No	No	
129	External 6 - Day 1		Yes	No	No	No	No	
109	FOTIOS KARZIS	BANK OF GREECE	No	No	No	Yes	No	
1	Francisco Javier López Pellicer	UNIZAR	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	No	
53	Frederika Welle Donker	Delft University of Technology	No	No	No-show	No	No-show	
74	George Christodoulou	Undergraduate student from the University of the Aegean	Yes	No-show	No-show	No-show	No-show	Day 2 & 3 double (P & O)
23	George Kalamitsis	Promitheas	No-show	No	No	No	No	
14	George Plavoukos	Mainsys sa	No	No-show	No	No	No	
84	Georgios Koursioupas	International University of Greece	Yes	No-show	No-show	No-show	No-show	Day 2 & 3 double (P & O)
29	Georgios Papageorgiou	Farosnet / University of the Aegean	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	
45	Georgios Priniotakis	University of West Attica	No-show	No-show	No-show	No-show	No-show	Day 2 & 3 double (P & O)
39	Gerasimos Maris (makmar)	None	Yes	No	No	No	No	
115	GIANNIS FAROPOULOS	Ministry of Health, GR	No	No	No	Yes	No	Speaker
26	Harris Alexopoulos	UAEGEAN	No	Yes	No-show	Yes	No	Day 2 double (P & O)
32	Héctor Ochoa Ortiz	Università degli Studi di Camerino	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	No	
52	Hendrik Delft	TU Delft	No	No	No	No	Yes	
69	IFIGENEIA VRATZIDOU	STUDENT	No-show	No-show	No-show	No-show	No-show	Day 2 & 3 double (P & O)
8	ILEANA VASDEKI	SKEP - ASSOCIATION OF SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY FOR CHILDREN AND YOUTH	No-show	No	No-show	No-show	No	

Id	What is your full name?	Which organisation do you represent?	Day 1 P	Day 2 P	Day 2 O	Day 3 P	Day 3 O	Comment
4	Ilia Christantoni	DAEM - City of Athens IT Company	Yes	No	No	No-show	No	
10	Ioannis Fytros	City of Athens	No-show	No-show	No-show	Yes	No	Day 2 double (P & O) Speaker
102	IRINI KONSTANTOPOULOU	IASIS	No-show	No	No	No	No	
13	Javier Noguera-Iso	University of Zaragoza (Spain)	Yes	Yes	No-show	Yes	No	Day 2 double (P & O)
15	Joep Cromptvoets	KU Leuven	Yes	Yes	No-show	Yes	No	Day 2 double (P & O)
37	Jonas Francisco Ferreira	Acre Federal Institute of Education, Science and Technology (IFAC)	No	No	No-show	No	No-show	
114	Kalliopi Bouraki	Independent Authority for Public Revenue	No	No	No	No-show	No-show	
117	Kalliopi Bouraki	Independent Authority for Public Revenue	No	No	No	No	No-show	
7	Katerina Karagiannopoulou	Institute of Communication and Computer Systems (ICCS)	Yes	No-show	No	No	No	
118	KONSTANTINOS PARIDIS	IAPR	No	No	No	No	No-show	
76	KOSTINOOU EVANGELIA	University of weastern Macedonia	No	No	No-show	No	No-show	
71	Kyriakos Kokkinidis	Student of computer science and telecommunications department arta university of ioannina	No	No	Yes	No	No-show	
79	Lazaros Karaoulis	DAEM S.A	No	No	No	No-show	No	
81	Leonidas Giasanakopoulos	University of Thessaly	No	No	No-show	No	No-show	
31	Liubov Pilshchikova	Delft University of Technology	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	No	
94	Maniati Krina-Nefeli	University of Aegean	No	No	No-show	No	No-show	
47	Manolis Ktistakis	Farosnet SA - Huffpost Greece	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Day 2 & 3 double (P & O)
93	Margarita Stasinou	Aristotle Uni	No-show	No	No-show	No	No-show	
50	María Elena López Reyes	Aalborg University	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	Day 2 & 3 online
78	Maria Eleni Bountola	Aristotle University of Thessaloniki	No	No	No	No-show	No-show	Day 3 double (P & O)
12	Maria Ioanna Maratsi	University of the Aegean	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	No	
75	Maria Zemperidou	University Research Insitute- Unicersity of Macedonia	No	No	No-show	No	No-show	
89	Marina Kola	Department of Mathematics,	No	No	No-show	No	No-show	

D6.6 Final Conference

Id	What is your full name?	Which organisation do you represent?	Day 1 P	Day 2 P	Day 2 O	Day 3 P	Day 3 O	Comment
		University of Western Macedonia						
54	Melanie Dulong de Rosnay	CIS CNRS	No	No	Yes	No	Yes	Day 2 & 3 online
103	MICHAEL VAGGOS	IASIS	Yes	No	No	No	No	
19	Mohsan Ali	University of the Aegean	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	
41	Myrto Pigidi	IASIS NGO	Yes	No	No	No	No	
86	NASOS PAPAS	M&O	No	No-show	No	No-show	No	
61	NIKOLETA IOANNIDOU	University of western Macedonia	No-show	No-show	No-show	No-show	No-show	Day 2 & 3 double (P & O)
116	PANAGIOTA ANAGNOSTOPOULOU	INDEPENDENT AUTHORITY OF PUBLIC REVENUE	No	No	No	No	No-show	
3	Panagiotis Pitsiniagkas	Me Alla Matia	Yes	No	No	No	No	
107	Panos Lolonis	Hellenic Cadastre	No	No	No	Yes	No	Speaker
111	Panos Lolonis	Hellenic Cadastre	No	No	No	No	No-show	
100	Patra Logotheti	IASIS	No-show	No	No	No	No	
63	Pavlos Potouridis	myself	No	No-show	No-show	No-show	No-show	Day 2 & 3 double (P & O)
101	PETROS FILIS	IASIS	No-show	No	No	No	No	
18	Ramya Chandrasekhar	CNRS	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	
28	Rikke Magnussen	AAU	No	No	Yes	No	Yes	Day 2 online
96	SAMEYULLAH NAJIMI	AL HAYAT TRAVEL & TOURS	No-show	No-show	No-show	No-show	No-show	Day 2 & 3 double (P & O)
91	Sevasti Georgiadou	University	No	No-show	No	No-show	No	
34	Silvia Cazacu	KU Leuven	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	No	
92	SKLIRI ARTEMIS	Democritus University of Thrace	No-show	No	No	No	No	
99	Sofia Papadopoulou	IASIS	Yes	No	No	No	No	
59	Sofia Tsekeridou	Netcompany - Intrasoft	No	No-show	Yes	No	Yes	
9	Spyros Gardikiotis	Bank of Greece	No	No-show	No	Yes	No	Speaker
88	STAVROULA SKLIRI	Democritus University of Thrace	No-show	No	No-show	No	No-show	
122	Stelios Sakaretsios	Minstri of Digital Governance	No	Yes	No	No	No	Speaker
105	Tantoulou P	UAegean	No-show	No-show	No	No	No-show	
73	Thodoris Papadopoulos	University of Aegean	No	No	No	No-show	No	
108	Thomas Hall	Bank of Greece	No	No	No	Yes	No	
64	Tzoanna Llesi	Ece	No	No	No-show	No	No-show	
17	Umair Ahmed	University of Camerino	Yes	Yes	No-show	Yes	No	Day 2 double (P & O)
112	VASILEIOS KRINIS	AAAE	No	No	No	No	No-show	
55	Vasileios Laopodis	CulturePolis	No-show	No	No-show	No	No-show	

D6.6 Final Conference

Id	What is your full name?	Which organisation do you represent?	Day 1 P	Day 2 P	Day 2 O	Day 3 P	Day 3 O	Comment
70	Vasileios michailidis	University of Peloponnese	No	No	No-show	No	No-show	
38	Vassili's Chryssos	Individual mapper	No-show	No	No-show	Yes	No	
30	Vicky Simitopoulou	Ploes RDI	No-show	No	No	No	No	
60	Viktor Deligiannis	University of Thessaly	No-show	No-show	No-show	No	No	Day 2 & 3 double (P & O)
68	Viktor Plasmas	The political science (first year) department of Dimokritio university	No	No-show	No-show	No	No	Day 2 & 3 double (P & O)
58	Yiannis Kotsis-Giannarakis	GR digiGOV-innoHUB/ GRNET	No	No	No-show	No	No	
113	ΒΑΣΙΛΗΣ ΚΡΙΝΗΣ	ΑΑΔΕ	No	No	No	No	No-show	
97	Κωνσταντίνα Τσαντή	Πανεπιστήμιο	No	No	No	No	No	

101	PETROS FILIS	IASIS	No-show	No	No	No	No	
18	Ramya Chandrasekhar	CNRS	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	
28	Rikke Magnussen	AAU	No	No	Yes	No	Yes	Day 2 online
96	SAMEYULLAH NAJIMI	AL HAYAT TRAVEL & TOURS	No-show	No-show	No-show	No-show	No-show	Day 2 & 3 double (P & O)
91	Sevasti Georgiadou	University	No	No-show	No	No-show	No	
34	Silvia Cazacu	KU Leuven	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	No	
92	SKLIRI ARTEMIS	Democritus University of Thrace	No-show	No	No	No	No	
99	Sofia Papadopoulou	IASIS	Yes	No	No	No	No	
59	Sofia Tsekeridou	Netcompany - Intrasoft	No	No-show	Yes	No	Yes	
9	Spyros Gardikiotis	Bank of Greece	No	No-show	No	Yes	No	Speaker
88	STAVROULA SKLIRI	Democritus University of Thrace	No-show	No	No-show	No	No-show	
105	Tantoulou P	UAegean	No-show	No-show	No	No	No-show	
73	Thodoris Papadopoulos	University of Aegean	No	No	No	No-show	No	
108	Thomas Hall	Bank of Greece	No	No	No	Yes	No	
64	Tzoanna Liesi	Ece	No	No	No-show	No	No-show	
17	Umair Ahmed	University of Camerino	Yes	Yes	No-show	Yes	No	Day 2 double (P & O)
112	VASILEIOS KRINIS	ΑΑΔΕ	No	No	No	No	No-show	
55	Vasileios Laopodis	CulturePollis	No-show	No	No-show	No	No-show	
70	Vasileios michailidis	University of Peloponnese	No	No	No-show	No	No-show	
38	Vassili's Chryssos	Individual mapper	No-show	No	No-show	Yes	No	
30	Vicky Simitopoulou	Ploes RDI	No-show	No	No	No	No	
60	Viktor Deligiannis	University of Thessaly	No-show	No-show	No-show	No	No	Day 2 & 3 double (P & O)
68	Viktor Plasmas	The political science (first year) department of	No	No-show	No-show	No	No	Day 2 & 3 double (P & O)
58	Yiannis Kotsis-Giannarakis	GR digiGOV-innoHUB/ GRNET	No	No	No-show	No	No	
113	ΒΑΣΙΛΗΣ ΚΡΙΝΗΣ	ΑΑΔΕ	No	No	No	No	No-show	
97	Κωνσταντίνα Τσαντή	Πανεπιστήμιο	No	No	No	No	No	
	Antonios Stasis	Minstri of Digital Governance	No	No	No	Yes	No	Speaker
	Alexandros Fourlis	Veritone Hire	No	No	No	Yes	No	Speaker
	Charalabidis Yannis	UAEGEAN	No	No	No	Yes	No	
	Stelios Sakaretsios	Minstri of Digital Governance	No	Yes	No	No	No	Speaker

Annex 2 – Presentations

Mapping Hidden Stories: reflecting on pedestrian accessibility in Athens

ODECO Final Conference – Day 1
14 May 2025 – Athens, Greece

 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

1

The ODECO Consortium welcomes you!

Beneficiaries:

Partners:

 ODECO

 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

2

1

Day 1: Mapping Hidden Stories: reflecting on pedestrian accessibility in Athens

Wednesday 14 May 2025

The first day will be centered around an attempt to map and enhance accessibility in the very popular archaeological and touristic areas in Athens and specifically around the Acropolis area, particularly for pedestrians with mobility-impairments, such as the elderly and people with disabilities. This session features a hands-on mapping exercise designed to identify accessibility gaps and determine the data needed for better navigation. By engaging stakeholders in this process, the event aims to shape research outcomes and promote more inclusive data practices, ultimately leaving a lasting impact on future visitors.

 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

3

ODECO – Open Data

Data is the new oil

Open vs. Closed data

Open Data is available

- Free of charge
- Openly licensed
- Machine-readable format
- Reusable

 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

2

4

ODECO goal

- To make Open Data Ecosystems sustainable

Open Data – Exclusive → Inclusive

Data should fit the needs of everyone

Maps are **representations** of our world, that fit certain views

We need to make maps that reflect realities not often represented

Program

13:00 – 13:30: Welcome & Introduction

13:30 – 15:30: Mapping session

15:30 – 16:00: Discussion & Reflection

16:00 – 17:00: Closure & Networking

 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

7

Introduction to the mapping exercise

 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

8

4

What to map

Look for ramps, wide doors, and clear paths.

Consider barriers like narrow doorways, uneven pavements and other obstacles that can impede movement.

https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Road_Curb.JPG by Michelle Arseneault under CC-BY-SA

 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

9

What to map

Look for tactile paving, audible signals, and obstacle-free paths

Consider hidden obstacles and that signage is accessible and visible

https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Gvidsistemo_por_blinduloj.jpg by Tokfo under CC-0

 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

10

5

What to map

Look for quiet spaces and areas free from sensory overload.

Consider noise levels, visual distractions, and comfort zones to find peace.

https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Caesar%27s_restaurant_interior_2019.jpg by Keizersunder CC-BY-SA

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

11

What to map – Other kinetic impairments

Look for resting spots, smooth paths, and easy navigation.

Consider areas that are comfortable and accessible, reducing the need for excessive physical effort.

https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Victoria_Centennial_Fountain_Victoria_British_Columbia_Canada_13.jpg by Michal Klajban under CC-BY-SA

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

12

6

What to map

Businesses

https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:20211031_athenes046.jpg by Jean Housen under CC-BY-SA

Streets and street furniture

[https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Tree_awkwardly_in_the_middle_of_the_sidewalk_\(42145762760\).jpg](https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Tree_awkwardly_in_the_middle_of_the_sidewalk_(42145762760).jpg) by Eric Fischer under CC-BY
https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:High_Street_-_gard_flower_pot_-_geograph.org.uk_-_2638533.jpg by Basher Eye under CC-BY-GA

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

13

Mapping Area - Groups

- 5 groups
- Around the Acropolis Museum
- Map slowly, the more detail the better!
- No need to finish the whole area
- Don't add details you cannot verify – better no data than wrong data
- Don't copy from other maps

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

7

14

Tools – Every Door

Map
Χάρτης

Businesses (stores, cafés...)
Επιχειρήσεις (καταστήματα, καφετέριες...)

Street furniture
Έπιπλα δρόμου

Download / upload
Λήψη / μεταφόρτωση

List of existing elements
Λίστα υπάρχοντων στοιχείων

Add new element
Προσθήκη νέου στοιχείου

Addresses
Αριθμοί οδών

Notes
Σημειώσεις

Change basemap
Αλλαγή βασικού χάρτη

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

Tools - Baba

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

Tools - Pen & paper

#	Element	Users Group	Accessibility Details
1	Bench	Wheelchair users, and parents with strollers	Bench is too close to the street and difficult for wheelchair users to access. Needs relocation.
2	Shop	People with visual impairments, Wheelchair Users	The shop has a ramp, but no braille signage. Narrow aisles make it hard for wheelchair users to move.
3	Sidewalk	All users, Wheelchair users	Cracked pavement, obstacles like trees and signs blocking the way.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

17

OpenStreetMap account (Every Door & Baba)

osm.org

Sign up

OpenStreetMap Edit History Export GPS Traces User Diaries Communities Copyright Help About Log In Sign Up

Log In Sign Up

Free and editable. Unlike other maps, OpenStreetMap is completely created by people like you, and it's free for anyone to fix, update, download and use.

Sign up to get started contributing.

Email

Your address is not displayed publicly, see our [privacy policy](#) for more information.

Display Name

Your publicly displayed username. You can change this later in the preferences.

Password Confirm Password

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

9

18

Questions?

Ερωτήσεις;

19

Mapping session in the Athens Acropolis area

 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

20

10

Program

13:00 – 13:30: Welcome & Introduction

13:30 – 15:30: Mapping session

15:30 – 16:00: Discussion & Reflection

16:00 – 17:00: Closure & Networking

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

21

Upload your data!

Login using your OpenStreetMap account!

Give map and table to organizers

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

22

11

Discussion & Reflection & Conclusions

 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

23

Welcome back!

13:00 – 13:30: Welcome & Introduction

13:30 – 15:30: Mapping session

15:30 – 16:00: Discussion & Reflection

16:00 – 17:00: Closure & Networking

 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

24

24

12

Open Data – Exclusive → Inclusive

Data should fit the needs of everyone

Maps are **representations** of our world, that fit certain views

We mapped = now we are seen (as we would like to be seen)

We need to make maps that reflect realities not often represented

ODECO

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

TU Delft KU LEUVEN CIB Universidad Empresa

25

25

Reflection steps

1. Welcome back – summary (5min)
2. Open/ pass the microphone (15min)
3. Open issues left (5min)
4. Closing, next steps (5min)

ODECO

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

TU Delft KU LEUVEN CIB Universidad Empresa

26

26

From the mapping

"We need a bigger measuring tape"

"Can you measure the inclination with your phone?"

"We can use sensors simultaneously"

"What is considered as accessible by wheelchair?"

"It should be 3cm, right?"

"Can we help you?"

"What are you doing exactly?"

"You cannot access the ATM"

"and the bathroom as well"

"these sidewalks are fine"

"No, I don't think so"

 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

27

Pass the mike

 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

28

Reflection 1: "the" data

What gets mapped?

Based on what? (e.g., common needs, common interests, etc.)

Is there something critical about what gets mapped and what does not get mapped?

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

TU Delft

KU LEUVEN

CIF

Universidad Empresa

IS

UNIVERSITAT DE VALÈNCIA

UNIVERSITAT DE VALÈNCIA

UNIVERSITAT DE VALÈNCIA

29

29

Reflection 2: **decisions** regarding data

What did the process look like?

How did your group manage to make their mapping inclusive?

Do you feel that you achieved your goal?

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

TU Delft

KU LEUVEN

CIF

Universidad Empresa

IS

UNIVERSITAT DE VALÈNCIA

UNIVERSITAT DE VALÈNCIA

UNIVERSITAT DE VALÈNCIA

30

30

15

Reflection 3: the **tools**

What tools did you use?
 Did they influence how you mapped?
 Did the tools influence what you/we consider as data?

 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

31

31

What else?

Is there something you would like to share? (negative/positive)
 Any surprising result from this mapping event?

 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

32

32

16

Conclusion

From inclusion to equity

Inclusion is a **static** concept (we are included in what already exist), while equity is a **dynamic** one (we change power structures, we change reality)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

33

33

Closure & Networking

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

17

34

Networking drinks

 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

Thank you for your attention

 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

37

38

19

Program

Start time	End time	Description
09:00	09:20	Registration
09:20	09:30	Welcome remarks by the scientific coordinator of the ODECO project
09:30	09:45	Open data in government by Christos Boukoros, Deputy Minister of Digital Governance
09:45	10:45	Session 1: Open data ecosystems beyond open government data
10:45	11:15	Table discussion session 1 accompanied by coffee
11:15	11:25	Reflection Session 1
11:25	12:25	Session 2: Emerging technologies for open data
12:25	13:30	Lunch
13:30	14:00	Table discussion session 2 accompanied by coffee
14:00	14:10	Reflection Session 2
14:10	15:10	Session 3: Power dynamics in the generation, use and regulation of open data
15:10	15:25	Short Break
15:25	15:55	Table discussion session 3 accompanied by coffee
15:55	16:15	Reflection Session 3
16:15	17:35	Session 4: Looking back to plan for the future
17:35	18:00	Closing remarks

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

39

Welcome by the
scientific coordinator of the
ODECO project

Dr. Bastiaan van Loenen
Delft University of Technology

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

40

20

The ODECO Consortium welcomes you!

Beneficiaries:

Partners:

 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

41

Day 2: Academic Track –

Thursday 15 May 2025

This day is the academic track of the conference and centered around our ESRs who will be showcasing their research outcomes within the ODECO project. The presentations of the ESRs will be structured around thematic sessions covering technology, business, public sector, and citizens & non-profit organizations. Upon the conclusion of the presentations in each thematic session a cross-sector discussion split in different round tables will ensue.

 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

42

21

Challenges

1. Lack of skilled people to use open data.
2. Current open data ecosystems lag behind in value creation.
3. Existing open data ecosystems are neither user-driven nor balance demand-supply
4. Existing open data ecosystems are linear.
5. Current open data ecosystems are exclusive.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

43

Current situation

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

44

22

45

Overall objective

To train a new generation of creative and innovative early-stage open data researchers, able to face current and future challenges, in the establishment of sustainable open data **ecosystems** supporting the EU ambitions to become a worldwide leading information economy.

ODECO

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

46

23

47

ODECO Early Stage Researchers (ESRs)

ODECO

Early Stage Researchers

 Davide Di Staso <small>PhD student (ESR01)</small>	 Dagoberto Herrera <small>PhD student (ESR02)</small>	 Silvia Cazacu-Bucica <small>PhD student (ESR03)</small>	 Ramya Chandrasekhar <small>PhD student (ESR04)</small>
 Mohsan Ali <small>PhD student (ESR05)</small>	 Maria Elena Lopez Reyes <small>PhD student (ESR06)</small>	 Maria Ioanna Maratsi <small>PhD student (ESR07)</small>	 Abdul Aziz <small>PhD student (ESR08)</small>
 Giorgos Papageorgiou <small>PhD student (ESR09)</small>	 Alejandra Celis Vargas <small>PhD student (ESR10)</small>	 Liubov Pitschikova <small>PhD student (ESR11)</small>	 Caterina Santoro <small>PhD student (ESR12)</small>
 Héctor Ochoa Ortiz <small>PhD student (ESR13)</small>	 Umair Ahmed <small>PhD student (ESR14)</small>	 Ashraf Shaharudin <small>PhD student (ESR15)</small>	

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

48

Program

Start time	End time	Description
09:00	09:20	Registration
09:20	09:30	Welcome remarks by the scientific coordinator of the ODECO project
09:30	09:45	Open data in government by Christos Boukoros, Deputy Minister of Digital Governance
09:45	10:45	Session 1: Open data ecosystems beyond open government data
10:45	11:15	Table discussion session 1 accompanied by coffee
11:15	11:25	Reflection Session 1
11:25	12:25	Session 2: Emerging technologies for open data
12:25	13:30	Lunch
13:30	14:00	Table discussion session 2 accompanied by coffee
14:00	14:10	Reflection Session 2
14:10	15:10	Session 3: Power dynamics in the generation, use and regulation of open data
15:10	15:25	Short Break
15:25	15:55	Table discussion session 3 accompanied by coffee
15:55	16:15	Reflection Session 3
16:15	17:35	Session 4: Looking back to plan for the future
17:35	18:00	Closing remarks

 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

49

Open data in governance by Christos Boukoros, Deputy Minister of Digital Governance

 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

50

25

Session 1: Open data ecosystems beyond open government data

Start time	End time	Description
09:45	10:45	Session 1: Open data ecosystems beyond open government data Moderator: Caterina Santoro (ESR12) Speakers: Ashraf Shaharudin (ESR15) Giorgos Papageorgiou (ESR09) Héctor Ochoa Ortiz (ESR13) Mohsan Ali (ESR05) Liubov Pilshchikova (ESR11)
10:45	11:15	Table discussion session 1 accompanied by coffee
11:15	11:25	Reflection Session 1

 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

51

Business models of open data intermediaries for a sustainable open data ecosystem

Ashraf Shaharudin

Department of Urbanism, Faculty of Architecture & the Built Environment

26

52

5 in 10

53

1. Open data intermediaries are not just a 'bridge' between open data providers and end-users

Technical infrastructure to contribute and use OpenStreetMap (OSM) data

54

27

2. Governments are no longer the (only) centre of gravity in the ODE

STATEMENT TO DISCUSS

55

3. Open data intermediation business models do not have to rely on generating revenue only or mainly from open data products/services

28

56

4. User-driven and supplier-driven are two sides of the same coin

Top ten countries with the largest OSM edits by different companies, 2015 - 2020

Amazon	Apple	Uber	Meta	Microsoft
US	Brazil	New Zealand	India	Australia
UK	Mexico	India	Thailand	Serbia
Germany	Indonesia	Philippines	Indonesia	Peru
Italy	Philippines	Japan	Vietnam	Venezuela
India	Russia	Kenya	Malaysia	US
Canada	South Africa	Colombia	Tanzania	Indonesia
France	Malaysia	Mexico	South Africa	New Zealand
UAE	China	Brazil	US	Myanmar
Spain	Chile	United States	Laos	Fiji
Kenya	Ukraine	Egypt	Myanmar	Nigeria

57

5. Purpose-directed approach is counter-intuitive to the philosophy of open data

"It's re-use of data in new - and often unexpected - ways that creates both social value and opportunities for economic growth. **It's not our job to say where data might be useful; it's our job to unleash it** and allow businesses and independent developers to build innovative services which they can then deliver to users. That's the story of technology through the years - and the way the World Wide Web itself has grown over the last twenty years."

(Berners-Lee & Shadbolt, 2010)

58

Thank you for your attention

59

Data Journalism – Adoption, Utilisation and Value Transformation

Georgios Papageorgiou (ESR9)

University of the Aegean / Huffpost Greece

Athens, 15-05-2025

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

60

30

Background: Open Data in Journalism

Open data can transform journalism by enhancing transparency and accountability.

Despite their availability, effective use remains limited to specialists.

Key issues:

- Slow integration into stories
- Fragmented and inconsistent sources
- High technical skills requirements
- Understanding the meaning of data

61

Research Questions

1. How do journalists currently utilize open data?
2. What challenges do they face?
3. What must media organizations do to integrate open data effectively?

62

31

Main Outcomes - Context understanding is as critical as technical skill

- Technical skills alone are insufficient.
- Context shapes the meaning of data.
- Data without context can mislead or lack relevance.

63

Main Outcomes - Journalists value processed data but are hesitant to share

- Journalists see analyzed data as an internal resource after putting in effort.
- Even large organizations share limited data, offering mostly tools for data analysis
- Journalists act more on the side of the consumer than the producer of open data.

64

32

Main Outcomes - Open data can lead to impactful journalism, but ...

- Create clear, newsroom-specific guidelines for integrating open data into journalistic practices.
- Build internal capacity by giving journalists the skills and time needed to work effectively with open data.
- While maturity models exist for releasing open data, media organizations lack similar frameworks.
- A new open data maturity model is needed, offering clear steps for adoption and ways to generate and measure value beyond direct financial returns.

65

Main Outcomes - Information Access Threats

Data Removals: Systematic withdrawal of previously accessible datasets.

Platform Policy Changes: Shifting access rules by digital platforms limit the availability of data.

Website Changes: Alterations to official online content compromise the continuity and traceability of public information.

66

33

Main Outlook

- Provide journalists with low-risk, actionable steps to use open data.
- Measure value beyond direct financial returns.
- Guarantee long-term availability of datasets.
- Include clear metadata and domain-specific context in data sets.

67

Proposition

Open data offers journalists access to vast information, but integrating it into their workflow requires new skills and methods.

Current business models prioritize audience engagement, making it difficult to monetize time-intensive, specialized data.

New metrics are needed to separate revenue for news stream and investigative reporting using open data.

68

34

Thank you!

69

Commercial organizations contribution to a Geographical Open Data Ecosystem

Héctor Ochoa-Ortiz

ESR 13

Università degli Studi di Camerino, Italy

15th May 2025 - ODECO Final Conference
Athens, Greece

 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

70

35

Methodology

Semi-structured interviews

25 companies

(7 big corp., 18 SMEs)

+ Overture Maps Foundation

71

Methodology

Source: Iulian Thomas "Weedstation", under commission from Héctor Ochoa Ortiz

Among questions asked:

- Describe your organization
- How does your organization use OSM and other data sources?
- How and why does your organization contribute to OSM?
- Barriers to contribution
- Strengths and weaknesses
- Contact with other stakeholders

72

36

Why and how are companies using OSM data?

Quality combined with **open license**

Google Maps

- Expensive, no real access to data

OpenStreetMap

- Gives true access to the underlying data
- license allows commercial use

73

Why and how are companies using OSM data?

One-stop shop

Open Government Data

- Good quality
- Spread out data sources
- Not commercially profitable

OpenStreetMap

- One place for all your geodata needs

74

37

Why and how are companies using OSM data?

Community

Vibrant community that maintains the data

Ecosystem of tools

OSM is alive

Allows companies to focus on **services** → mostly VAR

75

Contribution comes in value, not only data

Five contribution ways were identified:

- Database editing
- Tool development / funding
- OSMF / local chapters / HOT funding
- Event sponsoring
- Community building

76

Motivations, barriers to contribute

Motivations, ordered by most mentioned:

- Improve data quality
- Build a community
- Align with own dataset
- Grateful and want to give back
- We are part of the "open" movement
- Project/client requirement
- OSM is an important service

77

Motivations, barriers to contribute

Motivations, ordered by most mentioned:

- Improve data quality
- Build a community
- Align with own dataset
- Grateful and want to give back
- We are part of the "open" movement
- Project/client requirement
- OSM is an important service

Mixture of
own / private value
 and
social value

OSM has to turn private values into **public good**

78

Motivations, barriers to contribute

Barriers, ordered by most mentioned:

- Data integration
- Lack of tooling
- Community pushback
- License
- Lack of funds
- Lack of manpower
- Lack of time
- Lack of ground truth information
- Information on how to map for beginners

79

Motivations, barriers to contribute

Barriers, ordered by most mentioned:

- Data integration
- Lack of tooling
- Community pushback
- License
- Lack of funds
- Lack of manpower
- Lack of time
- Lack of ground truth information
- Information on how to map for beginners

Big corporations complain about
community pushback

SMEs complain about
lack of resources

Both agree on
data integration issues, lack of tooling and license

80

40

Overture Maps: response to OSM's barriers

Tooling availability

Data schema

Community pushback

Import Guidelines

Overture Maps: developers

OSM: community

Impact on OSM? Too early to measure

81

Discussion

Companies use OSM to enrich their services:

Quality, Open license, One-stop shop, Community

They also contribute back, not only with data:

Motivations are a mixture of private values and social values

How to turn private motivations into social good?

Barriers exist: Technical and governance

Companies want to align their contribution to their interests

Overture Maps as a response

82

Proposition

Actors contribute to the ecosystem based on **their motivations**

Aligning them to data contribution is **key** to making an ecosystem **sustainable**

When there are barriers, actors can ally to overcome them
...at the expense of other actors?

83

Bedankt
Merci
Gracias
Thank you
Ευχαριστώ
Tak
Grazie

hector.ochoaortiz
@unicam.it

odeco-research.eu

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

84

42

Mohsan Ali

ESR#5

- **Bio**
 - ✓ Pakistani (South Asia)
 - ✓ Lived in the Capital city of Pakistan; Islamabad
 - ✓ Studying at the University of the Aegean, Samos Greece (south-eastern Europe)
- **Experience**
 - ✓ ODECO-ESR (2022- Continue)
 - ✓ Research Associate, National centre for cyber security(NCCS), Pakistan(2020-2021)
 - ✓ Research Assistant, Air University, Islamabad(2018-2020)
- **Education**
 - ✓ PhD (2022 – Continue...)
 - ✓ MSCS(2018-2020)
 - ✓ BSCS(2014-2018)
- **Expertise**
 - BOLD, AI, CI, NLP, ML, DL, DS, BI, GAI (LLMs)
- **Find me on**
 - LinkedIn
 - ResearchGate
 - Google Scholar

85

Project Information

Research AIM

- To improve the technical interoperability of open government and non-government data at platform/portal level

Contributions

- Set of tools to improve the technical interoperability of open government and non-government data (Validator, integrator, etc.)

86

87

Open Data Technical Interoperability Validator

Designing: Open Data
Technical Interoperability
Validator

Methods: Systematic Literature Review, Desk research, Interviews, and case studies

Implementation:
Designing the architecture and the technology stack for the technical interoperability validation tool

88

91

92

Technical Interoperability Guidelines

93

Open Data Technical Interoperability Validator

Designing: Open Data
Technical Interoperability
Validator

Challenges:

- Adoption of different standards/Guidelines/requirements
- Availability of multimodal data/formats
- Varying open data policies and implementation strategies per countries/regions/global
- Diverse technological infrastructures (cloud based, edge based, etc.)
- Various needs for technical interoperability (standalone portal, compatibility with other portals)

94

47

Most Recently Publications

Sage Journals Search this journal Enter search terms... [Advanced search](#) I have access via: University of Aegean [Access/Profile](#)

Browse by discipline Information for

Information Polity

IOS Press Impact Factor: 1.3 [Journal Homepage](#) [Submission Guidelines](#)

Restricted access | Research article | First published online December 16, 2024

A Framework for the Multi-Dimensional Assessment of Interoperability for Open Data Ecosystems Development

[Mohsan Ali](#), [Georgios Papageorgiou, t-1](#), and [Francisco J. Lopez Pellicer](#) [View all authors and affiliations](#)

[Volume 29, Issue 4](#) | <https://doi.org/10.1177/15701255241297172> | [View article versions](#)

[Contents](#) | [Get access](#) | [Cite article](#) | [Share options](#) | [Information, rights and permissions](#) | [Metrics and citations](#)

95

Looking Forward To...

- **Communication & Outreach Channels**
 - ✓ All ODECO communication channels (Twitter, Facebook, LinkedIn, and ODECO website)
 - ✓ Conference presentations(ICEGOV, DGO, EMCIS, EGOV, PCI)
 - ✓ Journals (Information Polity, Online Information Review, TGPPP, Political Studies Journal and JEDEM)
- **Dissemination & Publications** – Can be found in the ODECO community on Zenodo and the website
 - Upcoming
 - Thematic Annotation of Open Government Data: Identified Problems and Tools for Automatic Annotation – **Under review**
 - Open API specifications benefits and adoption in open data portals – **Under review**
- **Collaborations** – Unizar, GFOSS, Unicam, and KU Leuven

96

Proposition

Achieving and quantification of technical interoperability of open data is very subjective and challenging task in the presence of different technological infrastructure and in the presence of diverse stakeholders in an open data ecosystem.

97

Thank you for your a

98

49

Non-profit organisations' value capabilities

Reducing open government data barriers for users

Liubov Pilshchikova (ESR11)
Delft University of Technology
Athens, 15-05-2025

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

99

Background

User Barriers

- Lack of skills and awareness
- Lack of usability
- Lack of community building
- Lack of governance
- Lack of accessibility and findability

Non-profit organisations (NPOs)

- NPOs are a type of open data intermediary
- Functionally defined by serving neglected populations, expanding the freedom or empowering people, advocating for social change, and providing services to the targeted groups, while not generating profits
-

100

50

Background

Capability Based View (CBV)

CBV - theoretical model that suggests that resources are the source of capabilities, while capabilities are the source of an organisation's competitive advantage if applied to perform important activities within the organisation

Open Data Value Chain

Research Question 1/ Method/ Outcome

Q1

What influence of non-profit intermediaries' value capabilities on the open government data user barriers has been identified in the previous research?

- **Sub-question 1:** What are the open government data user barriers in the literature?
- **Sub-question 2:** What are the value capabilities performed by non-profit open government data intermediaries in the literature?

M1

Systematic literature reviews on both open government data user barriers and value capabilities of non-profit intermediaries. **Linking barriers to capabilities** and validating them through workshops with academics in the open government data field.

O1

Linking the capabilities of the non-profit intermediaries to the barriers that open government data users face, based on the literature.

Research Question 2/ Method/ Outcome

Q2

What value capabilities do non-profit intermediaries perform to influence the open government data user barriers in practice?

M2

Case studies of NPOs:

- Open Knowledge Belgium
- CityLab Berlin
- Open Knowledge Germany
- Open Knowledge Foundation

OPEN KNOWLEDGE BELGIUM

O2

Gaining insight into the capabilities of the NPOs, the user barriers they influence, and differences that arise from the mission/type of open government data/user group/country context.

103

Main Results

104

52

Main Results

- *“Individual competencies” (knowledge and skills, personal connections and personal motivations)* are primarily important during the initial stage of acquiring open data
- The importance of *employees’ connections and personal motivations* is not present in the literature, although it can both motivate individuals to be part of an NPO and to focus on solving local issues with local OGD
- Capabilities across all the stages: *“Open data processes” and “Organisational capabilities”*
- *“Organisational capabilities”* consist of a *nonprofit organisational model, decision-making processes, and collaborations* with OGD stakeholders, which play a significant role in decreasing barriers
- The common user barriers across the value chain stages:
 - lack of open data skills and awareness
 - data usability issues
 - accessibility and findability challenges in the initial and final stages

105

Research Question 3/ Method/ Outcome

What influence do value capabilities of non-profit intermediaries have on the open government data user barriers from the users’ perspective?

Empirical test and quantitative assessment of the model via widely distributed **questionnaire**. The sample chosen will represent data-literate open government data users and their perspective on the role of NPOs’ capabilities in influencing user barriers.

Outlining the role of the NPOs as an intermediary in the open government data ecosystem for the users from their perspective.

106

53

Main Outcomes

- A conceptual framework to help non-profit organisations foster specific value capabilities to address their target user group's barriers
- Practical insights into the specifics of NPOs value-creating capabilities and their differences from for-profit or public organisations
- Visualisation of the prevailing user barriers and existing NPOs' value capabilities across the value chain of open data

107

Proposition

One of the value-creating capabilities of small-sized non-profit organisations is that their employees are *personally motivated* to solve their local real-world problems with local open data, which addresses the needs of citizens, engages them in open data use, and creates value for them.

To create a more user-driven, inclusive and circular open data ecosystem, the focus of other stakeholders should also be on *value creation for the citizens on their local level*.

108

Thank you!

109

Table allocations for ODECO ESRs and supervisors (others are free to join any group, ~9 participants in each group)

Table 1

Maria Ioanna Maratsi
Silvia Cazacu-Bucica
Charalampos Alexopoulos
Francisco Javier López-Pellicer

Table 2

Dagoberto Herrera
Caterina Santoro
Anneke Zuidervijk-van Eijk
Antonis Furlis

Table 3

Umair Ahmed
Ramya Chandrasekhar
Bastiaan van Loenen
Javier Nogueras-Iso

Table 4

Giorgos Papageorgiou
Mohsan Ali
Alejandra Celis Vargas
Joep Cromptvoets
Loukis Euripidis

Table 5

Héctor Ochoa Ortiz
Liubov Pilshchikova
Ashraf Shaharudin
Birger Larsen
Manolis Ktistakis

 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

110

55

Session 1: Open data ecosystems beyond open government data

Increasing need for diverse (non-govt) stakeholders in open data ecosystems, and new models for involving these non-governmental actors/stakeholders

Moderator: Caterina

ESRs	Relevant statement(s)
Ashraf	Governments are no longer the (only) centre of gravity of open data ecosystems.
Giorgios	Open data offers journalists access to vast information, but integrating it into their workflow requires new skills and methods. Current business models prioritize audience engagement, making it difficult to monetize time-intensive, specialized data-driven journalism. New metrics and business models are needed to separate revenue streams for news and investigative reporting using open data.
Hector	People and organizations contribute based on their motivations, aligning them to data contribution is key to making an ecosystem sustainable
Mohsan	Achieving and quantification of technical interoperability of open data is very subjective and challenging task in the presence of different technological infrastructure and in the presence of diverse stakeholders in an open data ecosystem.
Luba	One of the value-creating capabilities of small-sized non-profit organisations is their employees being personally motivated in solving their local real-world problems with local open data, which addresses the needs of citizens, engages them in open data use, and creates value for them. To create a more user-driven, inclusive and circular open data ecosystem, the focus of other stakeholders should also be on value creation for the citizens on their local level.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

111

Session 2: Emerging technologies for open data

Start time	End time	Description
11:25	12:25	Session 2: Emerging technologies for open data Moderator: Umair Ahmed (ESR14) Speakers: Ioanna Maratsi (ESR07) Dagoberto Herrera (ESR02) Umair Ahmed (ESR14) Alejandra Celis Vargas (ESR10) Abdul Aziz (ESR08)
12:25	13:30	Lunch
13:30	14:00	Table discussion session 2 accompanied by coffee
14:00	14:10	Reflection Session 2

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

112

56

Linked and Semantically Interoperable Open Data

Maria Ioanna Maratsi (ESR7)
University of the Aegean

Athens, 15-05-2025

 GScholar: <https://shorturl.at/lbsxs>
 LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/in/mj-mar/>

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

113

Background: Semantic Interoperability in a Nutshell

"Semantically interoperable schemas allow information to be automatically exchanged by sharing common meanings through the use of universally accepted standards."

Key aspects of semantic interoperability:

- Standard schemas
- Domain-specific knowledge representation
- Controlled Vocabularies
- Good metadata

Challenges remain..

! Inconsistent data vocabulary use, custom metadata schemas...

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

114

57

Research Questions

1. What are currently the semantic challenges of discovering and linking open data?
2. How can existing schemas be used across different domains to establish standardisation and cross-domain re-use?
3. How can emerging technologies (e.g., LLMs) contribute to semantic interoperability?
How can automated or semi-automated methodological approaches alleviate persistent semantic interoperability challenges?

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

115

Points of Progress..

- Categorisation of semantic interoperability challenges
- Ontologies and metadata schemas in the Cultural Heritage, Legal Sector, Archives. Semantic alignment methods.
- Semantic proximity and measurement of interoperability of datasets in a data portal.
- Status in metadata provision in major OD portals (US, CA, UK, EU, AU)
- Linked Open Vocabularies (LOV) structured analysis, cross-domain reuse possibilities.
- Exploration of potential of LLMs for cross-domain vocabulary alignment.
- Exploration of potential of LLMs for the structural enrichment of schemas such as wikidata, dbpedia etc.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

58

116

Main Outcomes (1)

- If someone tries to fetch "Concepts in X Discipline", there is no structured, uniform, or predictable way to retrieve content.
- Is it possible to search in a domain-agnostic way (search through "method", not discipline) and fetch cross-domain results?

Proposed methodology to improve the semantic hierarchical structure of knowledge repositories (e.g., Wikidata), enable interdisciplinary search retrieval.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

117

Main Outcomes (2)

- Align custom schemas (e.g., Riksarkivet) to standard ones, shift to Linked Open Data.
- LLMs may facilitate the process of semantic alignment and Linked Open Vocabularies (LOV) re-use.

Given an expert-validated dataset: Can an LLM perform the semantic alignment between a custom data schema and a standard one?

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

118

59

Main Outcomes (3)

Given validated mapping examples to a given knowledge domain: can an LLM recommend meaningful field correspondence to more vocabularies of the same or proximal domains?

Use Case: Cultural Heritage and Archival data representation

- Input validated mapping examples to other CH vocabularies (e.g., cidoc-crm, cis, cevent)
- Recommend further alignment to more CH vocabularies/ontologies (e.g., LOV) for enhanced metadata description?
- Recommend further alignment to other related domains to facilitate re-use?
- Identify new knowledge domain intersections to enable more advanced semantic search capabilities?

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

119

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

120

60

Main Outlook

- Machine intelligence and human expertise for semantic alignment and re-use of schemas and vocabularies.
- Cross-domain re-use of existing ontologies to facilitate interdisciplinary data discoverability and semantic search capabilities.
- Leverage the high potential of LLMs to facilitate semantic interoperability.

121

Proposition

AI Automation for semantic interoperability works best with human-in-the-loop. Our main concern should not be to eliminate human involvement but rather find the golden ration between minimum human intervention and maximum machine effectiveness and efficiency.

122

61

Thank you!

 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

123

Evaluating User Interfaces for Open Data Ecosystems

Dagoberto José Herrera Murillo
Universidad de Zaragoza

 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

124

62

Background

Open Data Portals play a central role in fostering data-driven innovation by enabling access to public sector data. However, most of these portals remain supplier-driven, linear, and exclusive, which limits their impact. This research focuses on the evaluation of the user interfaces of these portals, which act as critical mediators between users and data.

Discovery

Data Access

Data Evaluation

Data Ingestion

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

125

Research questions

1. How evaluation frameworks can be tailored to assess open data portals?
2. How user interactions with search interfaces align with mental models?
3. How collaborative data creation platforms can be analyzed through the lens of collective intelligence?

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

126

63

Methodology

A multi-case approach was adopted.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

127

Main outcomes

1. The TMAP based methodology revealed both strengths and design flaws of a semantic search engine.
2. Process mining identified significant mismatches between intended workflows and user behaviors.
3. The analysis of the HOT-TM showed challenges in achieving effective collective action.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

128

64

Recommendations

- Evaluation practices for open data UIs must go beyond technical performance and include user-centric and socio-technical perspectives.
- Interfaces should be tested for alignment with diverse user mental models and adapted to promote equity, clarity, and collaboration.
- Institutions should embrace flexible testing methodologies and iterative design to cultivate resilient and impactful open data ecosystems.

129

Proposition

How can we ensure that the rise of AI in digital open data platforms enhances the human touch rather than diminishing it?

130

65

131

Towards a FAIR Open Data Ecosystem using AI and CI

FAIR DATA PRINCIPLES

AH!

FINDABLE

DOI
10.1008/8.397

ACCESSIBLE

HOW DO YOU OPEN A .XZQ FILE?

INTEROPERABLE

HERE

REUSABLE

Umair Ahmed
ESR 14
Università degli Studi di Camerino, Italy

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

132

FAIR Open Data Ecosystem: Vision (AI & CI)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

133

FAIR Open Data Ecosystem: Vision (CI)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

67

134

Vision (AI & CI): Metadata Extraction (Keywords)

Model	Accuracy
T5-Large	53.4%
DeepSeek-R1-Distill-Qwen-1.5B	53.9%
Qwen2.5-1.5B-Instruct	60.0%
Llama-3.2-3B-Instruct	81.0%
Llama-3.2-1B-Instruct	57.3%
DeepSeek-R1-Distill-Qwen-7B	28.8%
Llama-3.1-8B-Instruct	40.3%
Mistral-7B-Instruct-v0.3	22.8%

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

135

Vision (AI & CI): Metadata Extraction (Themes)

Model	Accuracy
T5-Large	77%
DeepSeek-R1-Distill-Qwen-1.5B	17%
Qwen2.5-1.5B-Instruct	18%

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

136

Vision (AI & CI): Metadata Extraction (Description)

137

Vision (AI & CI): Semantic Search

138

Vision (CI): Crowdsourced Dataset Revising

The screenshots show the CKAN interface for the dataset '2021-2027 EU payment details'. The top-left screenshot shows the dataset overview with 'Data and Resources' and 'Additional Info' tabs. The top-right screenshot shows the 'Add New Revision' form. The bottom-left screenshot shows the 'Revisions' list with a 'New Revision' button. The bottom-right screenshot shows the details of a specific revision.

package	resource	revision
text id	text id	text id
char(100) name	text url	text original_resource_id
text title	text format	text ref_resource_id
char(100) version	text description	text status
text url	integer position	timestamp created
text notes	text hash	timestamp last_modified
text state	text state	
text author	text author	
text author_email	text author_email	
text maintainer	text maintainer	
text maintainer_email	text maintainer_email	
text license_id	text license_id	
text type	text type	
text owner_org	text owner_org	
boolean private	boolean private	
timestamp metadata_modified	timestamp metadata_modified	
text creator_user_id	text creator_user_id	
timestamp metadata_created	timestamp metadata_created	
jsonb plugin_data	timestamp metadata_modified	

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

139

Vision (CI): Circulating the Feedback Loop

The screenshots show the CKAN interface for the dataset '2021-2027 EU payment details'. The top-left screenshot shows the dataset overview with 'Data and Resources' and 'Additional Info' tabs. The top-right screenshot shows the 'Add New Revision' form. The bottom-left screenshot shows the 'Revisions' list with a 'New Revision' button. The bottom-right screenshot shows the details of a specific revision.

package	resource	issues	issue_comments	issue_log
text id	text id	text id	text id	text id
char(100) name	text url	text package_id	text issue_id	text issue_id
text title	text format	text resource_id	text comment	text author
char(100) version	text description	text title	timestamp created	timestamp created
text url	integer position	text body	timestamp last_modified	timestamp created
text notes	text hash	text category		
text state	text state	text label		
text author	text author	text status		
text author_email	text author_email	text priority		
text maintainer	text maintainer	text author		
text maintainer_email	text maintainer_email	timestamp created		
text license_id	text license_id	timestamp last_modified		
text type	text type	timestamp created		
text owner_org	text owner_org	timestamp last_modified		
boolean private	boolean private	timestamp created		
timestamp metadata_modified	timestamp metadata_modified	timestamp last_modified		
text creator_user_id	text creator_user_id			
timestamp metadata_created	timestamp metadata_created			
jsonb plugin_data	timestamp metadata_modified			

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

140

70

From Takeaways to the Way Ahead

AI4CI4AI:

- **AI (LLMs):**
 - Can recommend metadata (Keywords, Themes, Descriptions) to publishers effectively.
 - Publishers can either approve or furnish it further from which AI will learn to update itself
 - Prototype extendable and integratable.
- **CI (Revisioning and Feedback System)**
 - Github/OSM inspired revisioning and feedback/issue management system
 - Could easily be integrated as a CKAN extension
- **Mental Models Change**
 - So should agents that imitate them
 - AI reflecting CI and CI reflecting tuned AI

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

141

Proposition:

- Leveraging artificial intelligence for an open data ecosystem accelerates data curation by automatically cleaning, organizing, and annotating datasets, improving both findability and user accessibility

142

71

Bedankt
Merci
Gracias
Thank you
Ευχαριστώ
Tak
Grazie

Umair.ahmed
@unicam.it

LinkedIn

ODECO

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

143

Open data usage in elementary school

Towards learning designs to develop open data competencies

Alejandra Celis Vargas -ESR 10
Aalborg University, Copenhagen

14th to 16th May 2025

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

144

72

Problem: Lack of skills

Lack of skills for participating in open data ecosystems (accessing, understanding and using open data)

Elementary Schools
Generation of open data literate citizens

ODECO

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

AALBORG UNIVERSITY

145

145

Background: Open Data integration in school education

Identified potentials:

- Open data **connects** classroom activities with real facts.
- Open data increases teachers and students' **motivation**.

Drivers:

- Public engagement (awareness for active citizenship)
- Material for learning important skills (labour market and data-driven society)
- Connect school and other organisations (citizens science projects)

Gaps/ constrains:

- Focus on higher education
- Focus on exploration of Data as a tool for learning school subjects
- Focus on teacher's skills and motivation

ODECO

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

AALBORG UNIVERSITY

ODECO

73

146

RQ. How can educational designs foster competencies in young school students to engage in open data ecosystems and address real-world challenges using open data?

SRQ. What are open data competencies and the learning designs to develop them?

147

Methodology: Design-based research

148

74

Interventions in schools

5 interventions in 7th to 9th grade
117 students aged 14- to 16-year-old and 9 teachers

Data collection:

- Observations
- Surveys with students
- Focus groups with students
- In-depth interviews with teacher

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

149

149

The Open Data Newsroom

Physical and digital elements:

Three-phase process:

- Role-playing game to solve a mystery using open data
- Authentic game-oriented learning design
- Simulation of an authentic data journalism practices, three-phase process
- Solving a mystery by analysing visualisations of open data, data and contextual information
- Thematic analysis of interventions to identify 4 categories of competencies

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

150

150

75

Authentic open data inquiry

Data Literacy & Real-world problem solving

- Navigating open data
- Developing authentic data analysis
- Building authentic data arguments and stories
- Creating data representations

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

151

Conclusions

- An inquiry process
 1. Back and forth process from context to data
 2. Close relation between data and problem
- Authentic learning
 1. Personal authenticity:
 - Different data types and formats
 - Close to student's daily live
 2. Real-world authenticity:
 - Complex and ill-defined issues
 - Geographical local open data
 3. Professional authenticity:
 - Authentic open data practice (fragmented data, cross-domain)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

152

76

Enabling students to engage in open data ecosystems

Open data ecosystems in education
Local government, citizens, NGOs, school and young students (e.g. green schools)

Local experts

 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

153

STATEMENT

Technical and user-driven perspectives must come together to develop practical solutions that enable students and other non-data experts to participate in Open Data ecosystems. Currently, these fields operate in silos rather than as interconnected dimensions of a solution

154

77

Thank you for your attention

Alejandra Celis Vargas

cacv@ikp.aau.dk

Aalborg University, Copenhagen
Department of communication and
psychology

 This project has received funding from the European Union
Innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie

155

Abdul Aziz
ESR 08
University of Zaragoza

Universidad
Zaragoza

15th May 2025 - ODECO Final Conference
Athens, Greece

156

78

About Me

3+ years of industrial and academic experience, actively engaged in the field of Open Data and passionate about being the bridge between industry and academia

Academic background

BS in Computer Science

MS in Computer Science

National University
of computer and emerging sciences

Professional experience

National University
of computer and emerging sciences

UNIVERSITÀ
DELLA CALABRIA

Hiking and Travelling, favourite country

PhD Project

Technical aspects for inclusiveness across user domains in open data portals

Hosting institute: University of Zaragoza

Secondment:

ΠΑΝΕΠΙΣΤΗΜΙΟ
ΑΙΤΑΙΟΥ
UNIVERSITY OF THE
AEGEAN
Academic

Supervisory team:

Francisco Javier López-Pellicer

Javier Nogueras-Iso

157

Technical aspects for inclusiveness across user domains in open data portals

The implementation of Open Data initiatives is very narrow and disjointed, with **little participation from prospective users**. This situation underscores the **need for inclusivity** inside the Open Data ecosystem.

We need to identify **who are the Open Data actors**, **what are their technical needs**, and with the perspective of the governance and policy makers **what should be the roles** for the Open Data actors.

Objective: The main objective is to investigate **methodologies for the inclusiveness** in open data portals to enhance **accessibility** and the **user interaction** with open data portals.

158

Research Questions

- ❖ RQ1 – Is it possible to adopt a supplier-driven approach for inclusiveness?
- ❖ RQ2 – Can we improve the inclusiveness since the design of the backend through a proper curation and annotation of datasets?
- ❖ RQ3 – Is it possible to adopt a user-driven approach for inclusiveness?
- ❖ RQ4 – How can we transform users into the main actors of open data ecosystems?

159

Main Outcomes (1)

PUBLISHED

- ❖ A method for the analysis of feedback through social networks. This method allows us to compare the evolution and maturity of user engagement through social networks in different Open Data initiatives.

Identifying the Evolution of Open Government Data Initiatives and Their User Engagement

ABDUL AZIZ[✉], (Member, IEEE), DAGOBERTO JOSÉ HERRERA-MURILLO, JAVIER NOGUERAS-ISO[✉], JAVIER LACASTA, AND FRANCISCO J. LOPEZ-PELLICER[✉]

160

80

Main Outcomes (2)

UNDER REVIEW

- ❖ A supplier-driven approach for inclusiveness: A framework for the thematic annotation of open government data. The framework provides and compares the performance of different machine learning classification techniques considering both annotated and not annotated metadata corpora.

161

Main Outcomes (3)

UNDER REVIEW

- ❖ A user-driven approach for inclusiveness: A conceptual definition of roundtrip feedback in open data portals. We provide design guidelines to bridge stakeholder needs, improve data quality, and strengthen user engagement.

162

Further Progress...

- ❖ Will start working on storymaps,
 - ❖ a mechanism for inclusiveness

- ❖ Obtain a A2 certificate in Spanish Language in June 2025
- ❖ Completing 1st draft of my PhD thesis

163

Proposition

An open data portal without a proper feedback mechanism is a dead-end

164

Thank you for your attention

165

Lunch

Towards a sustainable
Open Data ECOsystem

Value Creation &
Ecosystem Sustainability

KEY FACTS

48	€ 3.9	8	15	37
Months	Million EU funding	Partners	Early Stage Researchers	Secondment

www.odeco-research.eu

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

166

167

Session 2: Emerging technologies for open data

Start time	End time	Description
11:25	12:25	Session 2: Emerging technologies for open data Moderator: Umair Ahmed (ESR14) Speakers: Ioanna Maratsi (ESR07) Dagoberto Herrera (ESR02) Umair Ahmed (ESR14) Alejandra Celis Vargas (ESR10) Abdul Aziz (ESR08)
12:25	13:30	Lunch
13:30	14:00	Table discussion session 2 accompanied by coffee
14:00	14:10	Reflection Session 2

The illustration shows a hand with a glowing blue light on the index finger, pointing towards a futuristic digital interface. The interface features various icons, including a bar chart, a gear, and the text "OPEN DATA". The background is dark with glowing blue lines and shapes, suggesting a high-tech or data-driven environment.

168

84

Session 2: Emerging technologies for open data

Role of technologies like user interfaces, portals and AI for improving findability, accessibility and usability of open data + how to design these technologies so that we can create inclusive open data ecosystems?

Moderator: Umair

ESRs	Relevant statement(s)
Ioanna	AI Automation for semantic interoperability works best with human-in-the-loop. Our main concern should not be to eliminate human involvement, but rather find the golden ratio between minimum human intervention and maximum machine effectiveness and efficiency
Dagoberto	How can we ensure that the rise of AI in digital open data platforms enhances the human touch rather than diminishing it?
Umair	Leveraging artificial intelligence for an open data ecosystem accelerates data curation by automatically cleaning, organizing, and annotating datasets, improving both findability and user accessibility + An open data ecosystem enhanced by AI is only as effective as the collective intelligence that continuously refines it.
Alejandra	Technical and user-driven perspectives must come together to develop practical solutions that enable students and other non-data experts to participate in Open Data ecosystems. Currently, these fields operate in silos rather than as interconnected dimensions of a solution"
Abdul	An open data portal without a proper feedback mechanism is a dead-end

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

169

Session 3: Power dynamics in the generation, use and regulation of open data

Start time	End time	Description
14:10	15:10	Session 3: Power dynamics in the generation, use and regulation of open data Moderator: Ioanna Maratsi (ESR07) Speakers: Silvia Cazacu-Bucica (ESR03) Caterina Santoro (ESR12) Ramya Chandrasekhar (ESR04) Malena Lopez Reyes (online, ESR06)
15:10	15:25	Short Break
15:25	15:55	Table discussion session 3 accompanied by coffee
15:55	16:15	Reflection Session 3

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

170

85

Towards Critical Literacy in Human-Data Interaction

Data Physicalisation Design to Reveal Entanglements of Power and Data

Silvia Cazacu (ESR3)

KU LEUVEN Spatial Applications Division Leuven (SADL) and
Geography & Tourism Division

GScholar

LinkedIn

Website

171

Background: critical data literacy

As a human-made artefact rather than a naturally occurring phenomenon (Kitchin, 2021), data is inherently entangled with power dynamics (Akbaba et al., 2024).

These power dynamics are evident in the human labour required to collect, process, and maintain it (Correll, 2018), the social, organisational and local contexts (Loukissas, 2021), and the values and ways of thinking at a given time (Kitchin & Lauriault, 2018), among others.

Despite these power dynamics, data is still portrayed as neutral and objective (D'Ignazio & Klein, 2020), preventing stakeholders to critically understand how their interactions with data affect their lives & to critically use data for personal and societal benefit (Pangrazio & Selwyn, 2023).

This lack of critical data literacy risks reinforcing dominant systems of power, privilege, and oppression (Collins, 1990) which further marginalises already disadvantaged communities (Barad, 2007).

172

Approach: data physicalisation design

involves the construction of 'a **physical artefact** whose geometry or material properties **encode data**' (Jansen et al.,

- enhances the **cognitive** understanding of data (Jansen, 2013);
- allows data to be **experienced** through multiple senses (Hogan & Hornecker, 2012); and
- **perceived** in relation to the whole body (Hornecker et al, 2023).

Fig 3: This 3D bar chart physically represents data about budget spending on education in European countries, between 1989-1999 (Jansen et al., 2013). Image: Y. Jansen.

173

Research question

How can the construction process of data physicalisation reveal the entanglements between power and data?

- SQ1. What are the entanglements between power and data during the infrastructuring process of data?
- SQ2. How can the construction process of data physicalisation reveal these entanglements?
- SQ3. What are the entanglements of data physicalisation as an infrastructuring process itself?

Chapter	SQ1	SQ2	SQ3
2 Ch2_Role of Values in Infrastructuring Mijn Tuinlab	●		
3 Ch3_Datopolis: Infrastructuring Critical Data Literacy		●	○
4 Ch4_EnviroMapper: Mapping & Interpreting Situated Meanings		●	○
5 Ch5_Power Dynamics in Infrastructuring Data Physicalisation	●	○	●
6 Ch6_KINnect: Balancing Power Dynamics during Infrastructuring	○	●	●

Table 1 shows the sub-questions answered by each thesis chapter, full bullets representing where the focus of the chapter lies.

174

Research outcomes

Chapter/status	S		
	Q	Q	Q
	1	2	3
2 Ch2_published (C&T'23)	●		
3 Ch3_under revision	●	○	
4 Ch4_published (CHI EA'25)	●	○	
5 Ch5_published (CHI '25)	●	○	●
6 Ch6_in progress	○	●	●

Table 1 shows the sub-questions answered by each thesis chapter, full bullets representing where the focus of the chapter lies.

175

Chapter 3 | SQ2: How can the construction process of data physicalisation reveal these entanglements?

Infrastructuring Critical Data Literacy through Role-playing Co-authored with Retrospective Study of the Game 'Datopolis'

Research question:
How can role-playing the process of infrastructuring support players to develop critical data literacy skills?

Methodology
 a retrospective qualitative study with two stakeholder, based on 27 interviews and archival data collected during an internship at ODI

#	Pseudonym	Player	# Played	Facilitator	# Facilitated	Experience (y)	Role	Seniority	Sector
1	Abigail	x	1			-1	data analyst	mid	private
2	James	x	6-10	x		2-5	software engineer	mid	public
3	Marjorie	x	1			-1	data analyst	mid	private
4	Tian	x	1			-1	data ethicist	mid-senior	public
5	Connelia	x	1			-1	data privacy protection	mid-senior	public
6	Taylor	x	2-5			2	data policy lead	senior	private
7	Peter	x	11-20	x		6-10	open data expert	senior	public
8	Marcus	x	2-5			1	data governance expert	senior	public
9	Betty	x	1			-1	data governance expert	mid-senior	private
10	Alison	x	6-10			8	data governance expert	senior	public
11	Will	x	11-20	x		11-21	data governance expert	senior	public
12	Sophia	x	11-20	x		2-5	data transformation	mid	non-profit
13	John	x				20-30	data skills consultant	mid-senior	private
14	Dorothea	x				2-5	data governance expert	mid-senior	public
15	Eddie	x	6-10	x		2-5	data licensing and IP rights	mid-senior	public
16	Archer	x				6-10	data governance expert	mid	private
17	Sören	x				11-20	data governance expert	senior	non-profit
18	Clara	x				2-5	data governance expert	mid	non-profit
19	Samad	x				6-10	data governance expert	mid	non-profit
20	Chloe	x	2-5			8	data innovation expert	mid-senior	public
21	Charlie	x					open data expert	mid-senior	public
22	Liam	x					data transformation	mid-senior	non-profit

Table 1. The 22 participants from public, private and non-profit sector had various roles and seniority levels in their organisations, all with different years of experience of playing Silicon Roundabout. We used pseudonyms instead of their real world names.

176

Chapter 3 | SQ2: How can the construction process of data physicalisation reveal these entanglements?

Results

How the construction process allows players to **develop new meanings**:

- 3 facilitation approaches,
- 3 play strategies,
- 4 discussion types happening in parallel with playing that demonstrate how players build critical data literacy skills

Discussion

- bridging theory in learning games (e.g. Peirce et al, 2008) with participatory infrastructuring (e.g. Frauenberger, 2019) by revealing how players often have conflicting agendas, but maintain their data infrastructure in spite of their differences, thus learning to be critical about how data applies to real world problems.

Fig 17. We mapped the results onto the game - play - world model (Juul, 2011) to present how the facilitation approaches and play strategies happen during play, as guided by the resources and rules of the game, according to play outcomes: Tools, Roles and Events. The metagame develops in parallel with play, combining metagaming discussions about strategies with examples of data practices from the real world, through metacommunication. With dotted, interrupted and continuous arrows we represented decisions belonging to facilitators, players and the game that connect the game, play and real world.

177

Chapter 5 | SQ2: What are the entanglements of data physicalisation as an infrastructuring process itself?

Disentangling the Power Dynamics in Participatory Data Physicalisation

- **published as: Silvia Cazacu**, Georgia Panagiotidou, Therese Steenberghen, and Andrew Vande Moere. 2025. Disentangling the Power Dynamics in Participatory Data Physicalisation. In the ACM Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems (CHI '25), 19 pages. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3706598.3713703>;
- awarded an 'Honorable Mention' recognition, for papers in the top 5% of submissions.

Fig 24: Methodology

- 1) Cross disciplinary ontology that synthesises literature from Participatory Design and Data Visualisation
- 2) Systematic literature review of 23 PDP artefacts presented in academic literature
- 3) Critical analysis by applying the codebook onto the corpus

Figure 23: First page of the publication.

178

Results

- 10 types of decisions that guide PDP agendas grouped as: WHO, WHAT, WHY, WHEN/WHERE, and HOW?
- 6 PDP agendas that present different orientations towards participation

Fig 25: By grouping the **totality** of decisions presented across all 5 ontological dimensions, we created a set of 6 PDP agendas: Pedagogy, Action Research, Practice, Engagement, Exploration, and Validation.

Table 2. The corpus of 23 PDP artefacts analysed with themes, subthemes, and codes that capture the most prominent decisions shared by stakeholders.

179

Chapter 6 | SQ1+SQ2+SQ3

KINnect

A Data Physicalisation Method that Balances Power Dynamics in Participatory Data Practices

Fig 28: Components: tokens, instruction cards, timers, ribbon and pins

Methodology:

- DP method with predetermined rules: how to use the physical components to encode data while ensuring everyone contributes equally
- Co-design of flexible rules with stakeholders who appropriate the toolkit for their goals
- Evaluation in participatory workshops + stakeholder interviews (post workshop)

Fig 29: Assembling model consists of annotations, token placement (discussions), ribbon and pins placement (synthesis).

180

Chapter 6 | SQ1+SQ2+SQ3

Preliminary findings

4 power manifestations (during co-design, construction, facilitation, and in the artefact), including:

- Workshop participants collaboratively creating new meanings based on individual contributions;
- Facilitators appropriating these meanings according to the stakeholders' agenda

Preliminary discussion

Tensions within balancing power dynamics:

- Prioritizing group dynamics over physicalisation input
- Balancing continuous consent with meaning making
- Tensions between artefact ephemerality and interpretability

Fig 30. In 3 workshops participants collaboratively create meanings and the synthesise them according to the stakeholder goals.

181

Fig 32: The thesis research process unpacks the entanglements between power and data through four layers, layers 1 and 3 by zooming out towards the infrastructuring of data, and layers 2 and 4 by zooming into data.

182

Discussion

Fig 36: From data to meaning: how each entanglement adds more context to data.

183

Statement 1

Power is embedded in data practices, influencing who controls, interprets, and benefits from data. Rather than being neutral, data is actively shaped by those who collect, curate, and use it often reflecting dominant ideologies and systemic biases.

When power asymmetries remain unchallenged, data practices risk reinforcing exclusionary narratives and obscuring diverse perspectives.

184

92

Statement 2

Data physicalisation has shown its potential to empower individuals to engage with data intuitively, transforming abstract concepts into tangible, personal meanings. By making data manipulable and embodied, physicalisation offers a more transparent way to participate in data practices and reshape the narratives that influence their lives.

185

Towards Critical Literacy in Human-Data Interaction

Data Physicalisation Design to Reveal Entanglements of Power and Data

Silvia Cazacu (ESR3)

KU LEUVEN

Spatial Applications Division Leuven (SADL) and
Geography & Tourism Division

GScholar

LinkedIn

Website

186

Open data meets data justice

Caterina Santoro
Public Governance Institute, KU Leuven

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

187

Background

Governmental Data

Data Gaps
Data Bias

Open Data

Epistemic injustice
in knowledge
production

Governance
"on us, without us"

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

188

We ask

How can we govern open data **equitably**? (in *theory* and in *practice*)

Advancing theory

Advancing practice

Conceptualizing open data justice

Equitable data collection

Equity and open data in literature

Equitable open data and public sector data sharing under the EU regulatory framework

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

In progress

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

(Some) results

- Public institutions play a role in distributing **power** through the data they choose to publish in open format
- **Epistemological diversity** can increase representation *in* data
- We need **loci (spaces)** for discussing data practices
- Data as **less than perfect** regulatory and governance focus

 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

191

My contribution

- Literature in critical data studies: from *critique* to **governance strategies**
- Literature in public administration: equity is a **dynamic** concept vs inclusion as static concept. We do not to include people in data, we need to **change** data altogether
- Socio-legal and governance: **regulation** and **governance** shape data sharing

 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

192

96

Global Trends: Staying Vigilant

NEWS
Donald Trump's data purge has begun

/ Health and climate information is already disappearing from federal websites.

by **Justine Calma**
 Updated Feb 6, 2025 at 4:52 AM GMT-1

75 Comments (75 New)

March 14, 2025

Image: Cath Virginia / The Verge; Getty Images

Donald Trump's data purge has begun," by Justine Calma, published in The Verge, February 6, 2025

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

Thank you for your attention

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

Legal strategies for non-government open data

Open for whom, open by whom?

Ramya Chandrasekhar
 Centre for Internet and Society
 French National Centre for Scientific Research

195

Research focus: Licenses and legal strategies

Licenses

Regulatory frameworks
 European Strategy for Data
A common European data space, a single market for data

Public-private partnerships
**Public-Common Partnerships:
 Building New Circuits of
 Collective Ownership**

**Legal instruments to open up non-government data?
 (Citizen-generated + private sector)**

Open data ecosystems as data commons?

- Law and political economy
- STS
- Commons-based governance

196

Research approach

Conceptual: Open Data Commons	Case study #1: Platform Data	Case study #2: Data re-use for AI training datasets	Cast study #3: Health Data
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Problem: Commodification of open data, enabled by law • Solution: Open data justice + commons-based governance 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Regulatory instruments in the EU for access to and re-use of platform data for research purposes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Secondment @ Inno3 Consulting • Report on legal challenges involved in re-use of openly licensed data and content from the open web for AI training datasets 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clinical trial data sharing and re-use platforms • Data re-use within the EU Health Data Space, based on principles of open data justice (with Caterina Santoro and based on a secondment @ KU Leuven)

 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

197

197

Findings: some challenges with non-government open data

• **Legal issues in the release of data as open data**

Proprietary claims in data(sets), data protection and privacy issues

• **Reciprocity v. Extraction from open data ecosystems/digital commons**

Commercial actors are less likely to respect and commit to license requirements of attribution and copyleft – see for example copyright cases against Generative AI companies in the US

• **Sustainability (especially in times of digital authoritarianism)**

Labour, infrastructure, funding

 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

198

198

99

Open for whom? Open by whom?

Why

Normative orientation towards **visibility, engagement with technology, and non-discrimination**

tion in the pursuance of **digital governance**

Data openness of training data

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

199

Openness

From cyberlibertarianism to digital authoritarianism... and back?

JOURNAL OF PEER PRODUCTION

Journal of Peer Production
ISSN: 2213-5316
<http://peerproduction.net>

Legal frictions for data openness

Reflections from a case-study on re-use of the open web for AI training

economic moose and legal categories could also inspire an evolution of the law as a regulatory system in order to integrate some of their technical features. This will lead to another kind of relationship between law and technology: after the control of technology by the law, which absorbs the new technology by expanding its scope of application, and in addition to the scholarship on regulation by code or of code (Lessig 2006; Brown & Marsden 2013) the law itself can try to integrate the technology. It might do so by reconfiguring its internal 'operating system' and shuffling the categories a bit more, instead of simply inflating them by adding an exception to the existing system.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

200

100

Results: some

- **Expanded univers**
Open Data Commons, AI-specific licenses (CC-BY-NC-ND), License, Open RAIL
- **Public procureme**
Digital sovereignty c

Recommendations for Sustainable Open Data Ecosystems

Data quality		
<p style="font-size: x-small;">1. Discoverability</p> <p style="font-size: x-small;"><i>A priori, ongoing and a posteriori strategies to involve all actors</i></p>		
Wide re-use		
<p style="font-size: x-small;">4. Beyond open government data</p> <p style="font-size: x-small;"><i>Power dynamics in terms of who and what is "missed out" in open data initiatives</i></p>		
Infrastructures		
<p style="font-size: x-small;">7. Usability</p> <p style="font-size: x-small;"><i>Funding, infrastructures and coordinating function of public administrations</i></p>		

Strategies

Elite Obodo License, Université de Montréal

201

Proposition for post-panel discussion

There is a politics of power to data, to law, and to the pursuit of openness. Some groups benefit, some groups are missed out.

How do we account for this politics in legal strategies for non-government open data?

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

202

*Openness has always been political.
So what kind of “open” future do we
want?*

 This project has received funding
innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 101019022.

 centre
internet
et société

203

Navigating Engagement with Local Open Government Data: Systemic Design for Participation in Urban Data Governance

María Elena López Reyes

PURPOSEFUL TECHNOLOGY LAB
HUMAN-CENTRED SCIENCE & DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES
DEPARTMENT OF COMMUNICATION & PSYCHOLOGY

**AALBORG
UNIVERSITY**

COPENHAGEN

102

204

RESEARCH FOCUS

Why Engagement Often Falls Short?

- Local Open Government Data (OGD) availability is growing, but data use is relatively low and difficult to sustain (Abella et al., 2017).
- Engagement strategies are often static and one-dimensional (Simonofski et al., 2022).
- Local governments often lack guidance on adapting their strategies to the changing contextual dynamics (Zhang & Li, 2024).

205

RESEARCH FOCUS

Beyond Availability: Why Relationships Shape Engagement?

- Engagement is not just about open data availability; it's about using, interpreting, and acting on it (Verhulst et al., 2020).
- Open data participation is relational, shaped by social, physical, and temporal boundaries.
- Without systemic thinking, strategies can miss key points of intervention.

206

103

RESEARCH FOCUS

What this Research Explored?

- How do relational and systemic conditions shape engagement with local OGD within urban data governance?
- Where are the frictions and leverage points for adaptive engagement strategy design?
- How can local public institutions be supported in evolving those strategies over time?

207

RESEARCH APPROACH

An Embedded Case Study of Purpose-Driven Communities

- 7 Purpose-driven communities of local OGD use.
- 5 Municipal infrastructures for local OGD availability.
- 11 Strategic local OGD advocates (in a co-design workshop).

208

104

FINDINGS
Engagement is shaped by Purpose, Relationships, and Lifecycle

- People care about something.
- Dynamic between personal goals and shared agendas.
- Engagement unfolds before, during, and after local OGD use.
- Understand when and how to adapt their engagement strategies.

AALBORG UNIVERSITY

209

FINDINGS
Engagement is shaped by Purpose, Relationships, and Lifecycle

- People care about something.
- Dynamic between personal goals and shared agendas.
- Engagement unfolds before, during, and after local OGD use.
- Understand when and how to adapt their engagement strategies.

AALBORG UNIVERSITY

210

105

FINDINGS

Engagement is shaped by Purpose, Relationships, and Lifecycle

- People care about something.
- Dynamic between personal goals and shared agendas.
- Engagement unfolds before, during, and after local OGD use.
- Understand when and how to adapt their engagement strategies.

211

OUTLOOK

A Method for Adapting Engagement Strategies

- Based on systemic design
- Grounded in relational understanding
- Co-developed with local actors
- Focused on identifying leverage points for strategy adjustment.

106

212

OUTLOOK Supporting Engagement as a Systemic Practice

- Map relationships, barriers, and enablers.
- Design strategies that evolve with community practices.
- Use co-design to align institutional capacity with public intent.
- Focus on timing, infrastructure, and meaning, not just tools.

213

OUTLOOK From Mapping to Strategy Adaptation

- Builds a foundation for participatory urban data governance.
- Provides a method for strategy adaptation, not universal solutions.
- Supports relational and contextual sensemaking in policy design.
- Opens space for future work on equity, power, and inclusion.

214

107

Thank You!

“Effective engagement strategies should focus on the needs and preferences of entire communities rather than just individuals.”

Malena López Reyes

E melr@ikp.aau.dk

T (+45) 5526 1503

W www.en.aau.dk

Aalborg University Copenhagen

Department of Communication & Psychology

Purposeful Technology Lab

215

Session 3: Power dynamics in the generation, use and regulation of open data

Investigating power relations and power dynamics in terms of who produces open data, what benefits it yields, and how to regulate open data

Moderator: Ioanna

ESRs	Relevant statement(s)
Silvia	Power is embedded in data practices, influencing who controls, interprets, and benefits from data. Rather than being neutral, data is actively shaped by those who collect, curate, and use it often reflecting dominant ideologies and systemic biases. When power asymmetries remain unchallenged, data practices risk reinforcing exclusionary narratives and obscuring diverse perspectives.
Caterina	Concerning the causes of open data-led inequities, we need to reflect on the imaginaries of deficit data. Data collection related to those we term “vulnerable groups” has a stigmatizing effect by assigning labels (e.g., deprivation) that have negative connotations, often rooted in preconceived understandings of certain social issues. Building an arena for contesting power dynamics is difficult if we rely on a deficit-based system for open data collection, which reinforces existing categories. It, therefore, becomes crucial to reflect not only on how data is framed but also on the politics of its creation
Ramya	There is a politics of power to data, to law, and to the pursuit of openness. Some groups benefit, some groups are missed out.
Malena	Traditional methods for engaging with open data typically prioritize individual users with a one-size-fits-all approach, overlooking the social and cultural factors that shape community behavior. Effective engagement strategies should focus on the needs and preferences of entire communities rather than just individuals.

 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

108

216

Session 4: The future of open data

Start time	End time	Description
16:00	17:20	Session 4: Looking back to plan for the future Moderators: Ramya Chandrasekhar (ESR04) Ashraf Shaharudin (ESR15)

 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

217

Closing remarks

 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

218

109

Thank you for your attention

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

219

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

220

Policy and Stakeholder Engagement

Friday 16 May 2025

 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

221

Day 3: Policy and Stakeholder Engagement – Friday 16 May 2025

The conference concludes with a session that brings together government representatives, industrial experts, practitioners in the field, policy-makers, to reflect on the project's outcomes and discuss future strategies for advancing open data ecosystems within their sector. This session offers valuable insights into evolving open data governance models and their implications for public policy and business practices. By participating, attendees will contribute to refining open data governance and fostering collaboration between governments, enterprises, and civil society, ultimately shaping the future of open data in Europe.

 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

222

111

Welcome by Prof. Bastiaan van Loenen, Delft University of Technology

223

Towards sustainable open data ecosystems

Friday 16 May 2025

224

112

The ODECO Consortium

Beneficiaries:

Partners:

 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

225

Challenges

1. Current open data ecosystems lag behind in value creation.
2. Existing open data ecosystems are neither user-driven nor balance demand-supply.
3. Current open data ecosystems are exclusive.
4. Existing open data ecosystems are linear.
5. Lack of skilled people to use open data.

 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

226

113

227

228

Overall objective

To train a new generation of creative and innovative early-stage open data researchers, able to face current and future challenges, in the establishment of sustainable open data **ecosystems** supporting the EU ambitions to become a worldwide leading information economy.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

ODECO Early Stage Researchers (ESRs)

Early Stage Researchers

 Ramya Chandrasekhar PhD student (ESR04)			
 Abdul Aziz PhD student (ESR08)			
 Caterina Santoro PhD student (ESR12)			
 Ashraf Shaharudin PhD student (ESR15)			

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

Towards a user driven open data ecosystem

- Open data ecosystems (ODE) are provider driven: users are not involved in decision making processes in ODE

231

From supplier driven to user driven

- A priori, ongoing and a posteriori strategies to involve all actors:
 - Inclusive permanent bodies
 - Promoting participation through open data materialization
- Who is in and who is out?

232

116

User groups

- purpose of use (explorer, aggregator, enabler, enricher, developer, and user);
- geographic scope;
- nature of the user;
- natural person or legal entity;
- user capabilities and understanding of the (business) opportunities;
- (access to) resources;
- (access to) technologies;
- frequency of use;
- nationality (local, regional, national, international);
- understanding of the (business) opportunities;
- AI as a user;
- etc

Non homogeneous needs that
may change over time

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

233

- No one size fits all

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

234

117

ODECO facilitating users

- User friendly user interfaces based on user mental models
- Technical interoperability validator (e.g., proprietary/ open format)
- LLM to facilitate semantic interoperability
- AI to recommend metadata

“AI with a human touch”

 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

235

Towards an inclusive open data ecosystem

- ODE is primarily government driven, also non-government actors should participate *with their open data*

 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

236

118

Towards an inclusive open data ecosystem

- There are non-government actors providing open data, Wikipedia, OpenStreetMap and also companies
- On the concept of inclusivity:
 - much more than “non-government actors should participate with their open data in ODE”
 - power dynamics in terms of who and what is “missed out” in open data initiatives
- Legal instruments, financial incentives and governance strategies for open data from non-government actors

 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

237

Towards a circular open data ecosystem

- Users of OGD should improve OGD and provide the new data back to the ODE (i.e., to the OGD provider) as open data

 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

238

119

Towards a circular open data ecosystem

- “All user groups examined are currently contributing **back to the ODE** and adding value through several different roles that they assume”, however it is typically NOT always improved OGD that is contributed back.
- Feedback mechanisms on open data (platforms)
- Legal instruments, governance strategies and possibly technological solutions to enforce circularity of OGD

 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

239

Towards a skill-based open data ecosystem

- Skill-based OD ecosystems focus on continuous open data capacity building
- Leverage education sector for data skills and data literacy
- Example:
 - through the Open Data Newsroom
 - (open) data science courses at all educational levels (from primary school to higher education)

 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

240

120

A sustainable open data ecosystem

- User driven, inclusive, circular and skill-based
- Training, training and training:
 - Professionals
 - Citizens
 - Students
 - Pupils

241

Open data ecosystem research

- Open data ecosystem research maturing
- Interplay between technology and governance strategies key
- Need to approach ODE through an interdisciplinary lens

242

121

Recommendations for Sustainable Open Data Ecosystems

Open data are crucial for scientific knowledge production, transparency and accountability, as well as innovation. The value of open data is multi-faceted, and include social as well as economic value. This includes the creation of new open datasets (often by combining or adding to existing open datasets), identifying social issues of concern, creating new technological infrastructures for open data, offering educational and awareness activities related to open data, and new data-driven products and services. However, open data initiatives and infrastructures also face many challenges ranging from lack of financial support to limited participation of non-government data holders, which impact their sustainability.

The ODECO (Towards a sustainable Open Data **ECOsystem**) consortium, a Marie Curie European project gathering 15 early career researchers, 20 academics from 8 universities and institutions, and 18 public and private partner organisations, conducted a 4-year interdisciplinary training and research programme on 'sustainable open data ecosystems'. The research and outputs of ODECO contain valuable practical recommendations on technical, social, economic, legal, governance and design aspects of different components of open data ecosystems. This document synthesises these practical recommendations for open data researchers, infrastructure builders, as actors, funders and policymakers.

The following set of recommendations is meant to support the future of open data, by imagining, building and maintaining open data ecosystems that are financially, socially and ecologically sustainable, equitable, and empower all stakeholders. Scan the QR code to read the recommendations!

R Chandrasekhar and M Dulong de Rosnay, Recommendations for Sustainable Open Data Ecosystems (ODECO Working Paper), 2025, 10pp.
Link on the ODECO website: <https://odeco-research.eu/?p=5106>

243

Thank you for your attention

244

122

Program

Start time	End time	Description
09:30	09:45	Opening remark by Prof. Bastiaan van Loenen, Delft University of Technology
09:45	10:15	Keynote by Els Breedstraet, Head of Open Data Innovation and Outreach, Publications Office of the European Union, European Commission
10:15	10:35	Open data in government by Antonios Stasis, Director General of Digital Governance
10:35	10:55	Open data in government by Ioannis Fytros, Coordinator of Open Government Partnership Initiative, City of Athens
10:55	11:15	Coffee Break
11:15	11:30	Open Data in business by Spyridon Gardikiotis, Director, Bank of Greece
11:30	11:45	Open Data in the Greek land registry by Panagiotis Lolonis, Head of the Directorate of Geospatial Information, Hellenic Land Registry, Hellenic Land Registry
11:45	12:00	Open Data in health by Giannis Faropoulos, Advisor to the Deputy Minister of Health
12:00	12:30	Suggestion of Policies and Strategies as an outcome of the ODECO Project by Prof. Charalampos Alexopoulos, University of the Aegean
12:30	13:00	Open Data in the workforce by Alexandros Furlis, Senior Vice President & General Manager, Veritone Hire
13:00	13:30	Networking drinks

 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

245

Keynote by Els Breedstraet,
Head of Open Data Innovation and Outreach,
Publications Office of the European Union,
European Commission

Publications Office
of the European Union

 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

246

123

Open data in governance by Antonios Stasis, Director General of Digital Governance

 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

247

Open data in governance by Ioannis Fytros, Coordinator of Open Government Partnership Initiative, City of Athens

**CITY OF
ATHENS**

 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

124

248

Intro

The Significance of Open Data in Governance

- **Transparency:** Open data enhances transparency by making government actions and decisions accessible to the public, thereby building trust in public institutions.
- **Accountability:** By providing access to governmental data, open data initiatives enable citizens to hold public officials accountable for their actions and decisions.
- **Citizen Participation:** Open data empowers citizens to engage actively in policymaking processes, fostering inclusive and participatory governance.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

249

"How it Started"

Brief History of Open Data in the City of Athens

- **GIS:** The Geographic Information Systems (GIS) of the Municipality of Athens have a long history which begins in 1994-7 and continues uninterrupted to this day.
- **Stores of health interest (KYE):** licenses for health-related establishments issued by the Municipality of Athens. For each establishment, a history of any transfers and general changes that have occurred is provided, as well as whether it has a permit for table seating."
- **Budget Execution:** provides citizens with the opportunity to monitor the progress of the budget execution in real time. In this way, citizens can utilize this data and become allies in improving the quality of life of all Athenians, but also to criticize using authentic primary data.
- **Open Protocol:** Everyone can see what stage a request is at based on the protocol number they have received.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

250

125

251

252

"What lies ahead"

Participation in OGP Local: A new chapter

OGP Local is a global initiative of local governments and civil society that aims to improve the quality of governance by increasing its openness. The basic goal of OGP Local is the self-commitment of local governments in relation to specific **open government measures** that they intend to take. In particular, the measures aim to strengthen **transparency, participation, accountability, citizen empowerment, the fight against corruption** and the **use of technological measures**, with the ultimate goal of **improving governance** and the **quality of life of citizens**.

Δήμος Αθηναίων

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

253

Conclusions & Recommendations

- ✓ Athens has established a foundation of open data practices through early initiatives such as GIS, Open Budget and Protocol registries - *even though it wasn't consistent enough over time (early adoption, multiple datasets, web services, JSON & SOAP access)*
- ✓ The discontinuation of key datasets reveals the need for sustainable, interoperable open data infrastructures. *(as seen with the Open Budget & Protocol migration impact)*
- ✓ The city's participation in OGP Local marks a new era of structured, citizen-centric open governance - *provided that it is supported at a political level (commitments on accessibility, transparency, participatory budgeting)*

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

254

127

+1 proposal

As we celebrate **transparency, accountability** and **citizen participation** (namely the principles of **open government**) through **open data**, beware the hollow sheen of "**OpenGov Washing**" – when openness is more a polished promise than a lived reality.

Why we need to coin the term "**Opengov Washing**" in Open Governance

Institute for Regulatory Policy Research, May 2025

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

255

Thank you!

ogp.cityofathens.gr/odeco/

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

256

128

Coffee break

Towards a sustainable Open Data ECOSystem

KEY FACTS				
48	€ 3.9	8	15	37
Months	Million EU funding	Partners	Early Stage Researchers	Secondment

www.odeco-research.eu

Value Creation & Ecosystem Sustainability

 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

257

 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

258

129

Open Data in business by Spyridon Gardikiotis, Director, Bank of Greece

BANK OF GREECE
EUROSYSTEM

 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

259

Open Data in the Greek land registry by Panagiotis Lolonis, Head of the Directorate of Geospatial Information, Hellenic Land Registry

 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

130

260

Open Data in health by Giannis Faropoulos, Advisor to the Deputy Minister of Health

 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

261

Suggestion of Policies and Strategies as an outcome of the ODECO Project by Prof. Charalampos Alexopoulos, University of the Aegean

UNIVERSITY OF THE
AEGEAN

 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

262

131

Open Data in the workforce by Alexandros Furlis, Senior Vice President & General Manager, Veritone Hire

 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

263

Closure & Networking

 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

264

132

Networking drinks

 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

265

Thank you for your attention

 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

266

133

Annex 3 – Posters

Evaluating User Interfaces for Open Data Ecosystems

A Multi-Case Study on Search, Usability, and Collective Intelligence

Dagoberto José Herrera Murillo (Universidad de Zaragoza)

dherrera@unizar.es

Background

Open Data Portals play a central role in fostering data-driven innovation by enabling access to public sector data. However, most of these portals remain supplier-driven, linear, and exclusive, which limits their impact. This research focuses on the evaluation of the user interfaces of these portals, which act as critical mediators between users and data.

Main outcomes

- The TMAP based methodology revealed both strengths and design flaws of a semantic search engine.
- Process mining identified significant mismatches between intended workflows and user behaviors.
- The analysis of the HOT-TM showed challenges in achieving effective collective action.

Research questions

- (1) How evaluation frameworks can be tailored to assess open data portals?
- (2) How user interactions with search interfaces align with mental models?
- (3) How collaborative data creation platforms can be analyzed through the lens of collective intelligence?

Methodology

A multi-case approach was adopted.

- A structured evaluation methodology for geospatial search engines.
- Process mining and usability testing to analyze user mental models.
- Collective intelligence metrics to evaluate data-sharing dynamics among humanitarian mappers (HOT-TM).

Recommendations

- Evaluation practices for open data UIs must go beyond technical performance and include user-centric and socio-technical perspectives.
- Interfaces should be tested for alignment with diverse user mental models and adapted to promote equity, clarity, and collaboration.

ODECO

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

Data journalism – adoption, utilisation and value transformation

Exploring the Realities of Open Data in Newsrooms

Georgios Papageorgiou (Huffpost Greece / University of the Aegean)
gpapag@aegean.gr

Background

In the past, journalists struggled to acquire access to data, but the rise of open data (freely available and in large quantities) has changed that landscape. Open data can be a valuable tool for journalists to enhance transparency, accountability, and the quality of news reporting, reinforcing their role as a pillar of democracy. However, its effective use is limited to specialized journalists, either within small, dedicated teams or larger media organizations that can afford to maintain expert data journalism departments.

Research questions

- How do journalists currently utilize open data in their journalistic practices?
- What are the challenges faced by journalists when working with open data?
- What are the key steps media organizations must take to effectively adopt and integrate open data into their journalistic practices?

Methodology

- Structured literature review to evaluate open data usage in journalism.
- Interviews with data journalists.
- Action research conducted in HuffPost Greece newsroom.
- Technology Action Research monitoring food price.
- Conceptual model development for a maturity model on the use of open data in journalism.

Main outcomes

- Using open data in news articles is often slow and offers no guaranteed outcome.
- The fragmentation of open data sources requires significant time to locate and verify their continued availability.
- Technical skills are only the first barrier, understanding the context of the data is equally demanding.
- Journalists view the processed open data they've worked on as a valuable resource, which they are generally unwilling to share freely.

Main Outlook/Recommendations

- Support journalists with concrete, low-risk steps to integrate open data and achieve tangible, impactful outcomes.
- Establish methods to measure value generation from open data that go beyond economic metrics.
- Ensure long-term availability of open datasets; provide guarantees of continuity to justify infrastructure and training investments.
- Ensure that open data be delivered with clear metadata and domain-specific instructions to help users understand the context.

ODECO

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

Commercial organizations contribution to a Geographical Open Data Ecosystem: the OpenStreetMap case

Héctor Ochoa Ortiz (ESR13) - Università degli Studi di Camerino, Italy

Motivation

Previous work on commercial organizations in OpenStreetmap has been focused on three topics:

- Anderson and Sarkar have studied corporate editing in OSM by identifying paid editors and analyzing their editing patterns through changesets.
- Schröder-Bergen et al. examined (de-)colonization practices in OSM, noting a shift from individual contributors in the Global North to a mix of global individual and institutional actors.
- Yang et al. analyzed the contributions of nine major organizations to OSM and found they reduced data inequality between countries from 2015 to 2020. Non-profits played a larger role than for-profits, except for humanitarian-focused corporations.

While the impact of commercial organizations on OSM has been studied, there is a lack of research on their needs, motivations, and barriers to contributing.

Results

Why?

1. Quality combined with open license
2. One-stop shop
3. Community

Motivations are a mixture of own private values and public social values
Aligning private business values with contribution to the Open Data Ecosystem are key for sustainability

How?

OSM database editing
Tool development and/or funding
OSMF or other related OSM NGOs funding
Event sponsoring
Community building

Companies contribute in multiple ways, depending on their business model
Big corporations have more resources to contribute in multiple ways

Barriers

Table 2. Barriers for contribution mentioned, ordered by most mentioned.

Data integration	4
Lack of tooling	3
Community pushback	3
License	3
Importing Guidelines	3
Lack of funds	3
Lack of manpower	2
Lack of time	2
Lack of ground truth info	1
Information on how to map for beginners	1

SMEs see more barriers in the lack of resources (funds, manpower, and time), in comparison with big corporations. Big corporations, on the other hand, feel more pushback from the OSM community, and their actions are under heavy scrutiny.
Overture Maps was created by corporations as an answer to the contribution barriers mentioned, plus usage barriers (so data is more developer-friendly)

Methodology

Semi-structured interviews

Table 1. Interviewed organizations, ordered alphabetically.

Organization name	Org. type	Org. domain	Org. HOs	Interviewee(s)	Int. based in
Asamm Software	SME	App dev., GIS	Czechia	2 employees	Czechia
Bunthing Labs	SME	AI, GIS	USA	Co-founder	USA
Con.sens Verkehrsplanung	SME	Urban Planning	Austria	Shareholder	Austria
Elastic	Big corp.	IT	Netherlands	Employee	Spain
Esri	Big corp.	GIS	USA	Employee	USA
Farmeye	SME	Agriculture, GIS	Ireland	Co-founder	Ireland
Geofabrik	SME	GIS	Germany	Co-founder	Germany
Gojek (GoTo)	Big corp.	Various, IT	Indonesia	2 employees	Indonesia
Graphhopper	SME	Routing services	Germany	Co-founder	Germany
Interline Technologies	SME	Mobility, GIS	USA	Co-founder	USA
Intevation	SME	IT	Germany	Co-founder	Germany
Kontur	SME	GIS	USA	Employee	Poland
Maptoolkit	SME	Cartography, GIS	Austria	Founder	Austria
Meta Platforms	Big corp.	Social networks, IT	USA	Employee	UK
MobilityLabel	SME	Mobility, GIS	Netherlands	Co-founder	Netherlands
OpenCage	SME	Geocoding	Germany	Co-founder	Germany
Overture Maps Foundation	Foundation	GIS	USA	CEO	USA
Plan4Better	SME	GIS	Germany	CEO	Germany
Protomaps	SME	GIS	USA	Founder	USA
Rinkai	SME	Mobility, GIS	Czechia	2 Employees	Czechia
Stadia Maps	SME	Cartography, GIS	USA	Co-founder	South Korea
StreetLight Data	Big corp. ¹	GIS, Mobility	USA	CTO	USA
TEconnecta	SME	Telecommunications	Spain	Co-founder	Spain
Thunderforest	SME	Cartography, GIS	UK	Founder	UK
(Gravitystorm)					
TomTom	Big corp.	Mobility, GIS	Netherlands	Employee	Netherlands
VK	Big corp.	Social networks, IT	Russia	Several employees	Russia

SME: small and medium-sized enterprise (<250 employees).

Future work

Analyzing the recent surge in use technologies such as microtasking by corporations to contribute data and do community-building, while avoiding the previous barriers.

Analyzing the creation of Overture Maps, and the effect it has had on the OpenStreetMap ecosystem.

Analyzing the collaboration between commercial organizations and other actors in the ecosystem.

References

- Anderson, J. 2021. "Jennings Anderson's Diary | a 2021 Update on Paid Editing in OpenStreetMap." <https://www.openstreetmap.org/user/Jennings%20Anderson/diary/396271>.
- Anderson, J., and D. Sarkar. 2020. "Curious Cases of Corporations in OpenStreetMap." <http://2020.stateofthemap.org/sessions/SPRQVZ/>.
- Anderson, J., D. Sarkar, and L. Palen. 2019. "Corporate Editors in the Evolving Landscape of OpenStreetMap." ISPRS International Journal of Geo-Information 8 (5): 232. DOI: 10.3390/ijgi8050232.
- Ochoa-Ortiz, H., & Re, B. 2025. Exploring why and how commercial organizations contribute to OpenStreetMap. Annals of GIS. DOI: 10.1080/19475683.2025.2457396.
- Schröder-Bergen, S., G. Glasze, B. Michel, and F. Dammann. 2022. "De/Colonizing OpenStreetMap? Local Mappers, Humanitarian and Commercial Actors and the Changing Modes of Collaborative Mapping." Geo Journal 87 (6): 5051–5066. DOI: 10.1007/s10708-021-10547-7.
- Sarkar, D., and J. T. Anderson. 2022. "Corporate Editors in OpenStreetMap: Investigating Co-Editing Patterns." Transactions in GIS 26 (4): 1879–1897. DOI: 10.1111/tgis.12910.
- Schröder-Bergen, Susanne. 2023. "Social, Technical and Political Transformations in OpenStreetMap – from Volunteered Geographic Information to Embedding Digital Commons in Platform Capitalism." Proceedings of the OSM Science at State of the Map Europe 2023.
- Veselovsky, V., D. Sarkar, J. Anderson, and R. Soden. 2022. "An Automated Approach to Identifying Corporate Editing." Proceedings of the International AAAI Conference on Web and Social Media, 1052–1063. Vol. 16. DOI: 10.1609/icwsm.v16i1.19357.
- Yang, A., H. Fan, Q. Jia, M. Ma, Z. Zhong, J. Li, and N. Jing. 2024. "How Do Contributions of Organizations Impact Data Inequality in OpenStreetMap?" Computers, Environment and Urban Systems 109:102077. DOI: 10.1016/j.compenvurbysys.2024.102077.

Non-profit organisations' value capabilities

Reducing open government data barriers for the users

Liubov Pishchikova (Delft University of Technology)

l.pilshchikova@tudelft.nl

Background

Small-sized non-profit organisations (NPOs) are a type of intermediary that can *empower communities* of open government data (OGD) users without financial gain.

According to the capability-based view, NPOs have specific *value capabilities* to help users *reduce their barriers* and stimulate OGD reuse.

As OGD use is lower than governments expect, addressing the user barriers can help solve it.

Main outcomes

- A conceptual framework to help non-profit organisations foster specific value capabilities to address their target user group's barriers
- Practical insights into the specifics of NPOs value-creating capabilities and their differences from for-profit or public organisations
- Visualisation of the prevailing user barriers and existing NPOs' value capabilities across the value chain of open data

Research questions

1. What influence of non-profit intermediaries' value capabilities on the open government data user barriers has been identified *in the previous research*?
2. What value capabilities do non-profit intermediaries perform to influence the open government data user barriers *in practice*?
3. What influence do value capabilities of non-profit intermediaries have on the open government data user barriers *from the users' perspective*?

Methodology

Methods for each RQ:

1. Systematic literature review
2. Four case-studies of small-sized non-profit organisations

3. Survey and model building

ODECO

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

Navigating Engagement with Local Open Government Data: Systemic Design for Participation in Urban Data Governance

María Elena López Reyes (Aalborg University)
melr@ikp.aau.dk

Background

- Local governments increasingly publish open government data (OGD) to promote participation.
- Yet data use remains low, with engagement strategies often fragmented, static, or ill-suited to community needs.
- Engagement needs to happen before, during, and after data is used, as a relational, continuous process.

Main outcomes

- ✓ A relational framing of community: not just citizens or users, but any actors sharing a purpose around local OGD, including public servants and advocates.
- ✓ An adaptive method to help local governments respond to emerging participation needs.
- ✓ Practical insights into how to foster participation across the lifecycle of local OGD.
- ✓ Visual and strategic tool for tailoring engagement to local systems.

Research questions

1. How is participation through local OGD in urban data governance shaped?
2. What engagement patterns emerge when communities interact with local OGD, and what helps or hinders these patterns?
3. How do local government infrastructures shape and adapt to foster engagement through local OGD?
4. How can engagement strategies be co-designed and iteratively evolved to support systemic, long-term participation?

Outlook:

- Engagement is not a one-time action triggered when a portal goes live, but a continuous, systemic process shaped by the relationships, structures, and capacities of those involved.
- Local OGD initiatives must be co-created and co-maintained, not just built and released.
- This work lays the groundwork for designing responsive, community-shaped strategies within urban data governance ecosystems.

Purposes		Interrelations		
		(1) Obtain	(2) Transform	(3) Sustain
Material embodiments	Solution-driven meanings	Operational	Technological	
	Collaboration-driven meanings	Strategic	Functional	
	Knowledge-driven meanings	Accountability	Regulatory	Ethical

ODECO

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

Cross-Domain Semantic Interoperability of Open Data

A Methodological Framework for Linked Knowledge

Maria Ioanna Maratsi (University of the Aegean)

ioanna.m@aegean.gr

Background

Sharing a common structure by mapping concepts and relationships between schemas enables interoperability, reuse, machine-processable and semantic search capabilities. Aligning custom schemas to standardised ontologies in their knowledge domain highly beneficial.

Challenge: Inconsistent data vocabulary use, custom metadata schemas...

Main Outcomes

- Proposed methodology to improve the semantic hierarchical structure of knowledge repositories (e.g., Wikidata), enable interdisciplinary search retrieval.
- Align custom data schemas (e.g., Archival Institutions) to standard ones, shift to Linked Open Data.
- LLMs may facilitate the process of semantic alignment and Linked Open Vocabularies (LOV) re-use.

Research Questions

1. What are the current semantic challenges of discovering and linking open data?
2. How can existing schemas be used across different domains to establish standardisation and cross-domain re-use?
3. How can emerging technologies (e.g., LLMs) contribute to semantic interoperability?

Main Outlook

- Best of machine intelligence and human expertise for semantic alignment and re-use of schemas and vocabularies.
- Cross-domain re-use of existing ontologies to facilitate interdisciplinary data discoverability and semantic search capabilities.
- Leverage the high potential of LLMs to facilitate semantic interoperability.

ODECO

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

Technical interoperability in the open data ecosystem

Mohsan Ali (University of the Aegean)
Mohsan@aegean.gr

Background

Main outcomes

- ✓ Challenges
- ✓ Requirements
- ✓ Standards
- ✓ Guidelines

Research questions

- 🔍 What tech commons (CKAN, DKAN) empower open data portals?
- 🔧 How to design/develop a tool for validating tech open data interoperability?
- 🌐 What are the main challenges in integrating open data from government and non-government sources?

Methodology

Recommendations

- 📁 Use open & machine-readable formats
- 📄 Apply DCAT, DCAT-AP Profiling
- 🏗️ Choose scalable tech infrastructure.
- 🔗 Ensure portal compatibility.
- 🌐 Provide open, license-free access.
- ⚙️ Improve interoperability regularly.
- 🔑 Offer RESTful, well-documented APIs.
- 📏 Follow W3C, DCAT, FAIR standards.
- 🕸️ Enable RDF, SPARQL linked data.

ODECO

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

LEGAL STRATEGIES FOR NON-GOVERNMENT OPEN DATA

Open by whom? Open for whom?

Ramya Chandrasekhar, Centre for Internet and Society, CNRS, France
ramya.chandrasekhar@cncrs.fr

Background

The open data movement has close connections with open government and has resulted in wider reuse of public sector information. At the same time, the open data movement also has close connections with open source and open science. This has resulted in demands for openness being extended to non-government data holders as well, such as citizens, corporations and research actors.

Main outcomes

1. Open data bears social and economic value. But, there is a politics to open data.
2. Commercial actors reuse open data, but contribute little back – either through the reciprocal release of open data or for the maintenance of open data infrastructures.
3. Legal strategies need to go beyond traditional open data licenses, to include other types of frameworks for data sharing and re-use.

Research questions

1. What is 'open data' in the context of non-government data holders?
2. What are the legal interests in data, that obstruct the release and reuse of non-government open data?
3. Who benefits from (non-government) open data, and who is missed out?
4. How should the law intervene in addressing the politics of open data?

Methodology

1. Legal analysis of legal frameworks for open data in the European Union
2. 3 case-studies:
 - Legal frameworks for reuse of data generated on and held by online platforms and search engines.
 - Licensing frictions in the reuse of open data and content for training foundation AI models.
 - Reuse of health data in the European Health Data Space (ongoing).

Main Recommendations

1. 'Open Data Justice' as a heuristic framework for open data (co-created with Caterina Santoro and Stefania Milan).
2. The importance of new legal frameworks for data sharing and reuse, such as researcher access to platform data under the Digital Services Act and data altruism under the Data Governance Act.
3. The need for additional licenses that account for reciprocity and sustainability, in light of extraction of open data and content by commercial actors.

ODECO

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

Towards Critical Literacy in Human-Data Interaction

Data Physicalisation Design to Reveal Entanglements of Power and Data

Silvia Cazacu (KU Leuven)

silvia.cazacu-bucica@kuleuven.be

Background

As a human-made artefact rather than a naturally occurring phenomenon (Kitchin, 2021), data is inherently **entangled** with power dynamics (Akbaba et al., 2024).

These **power dynamics** are evident in the human labour required to collect, process, and maintain it (Correll, 2018), the social, organisational and local contexts (Loukissas, 2021), and the values and ways of thinking at a given time (Kitchin & Lauriault, 2018), among others.

Despite these power dynamics, data is still portrayed as neutral and objective (D'Ignazio & Klein, 2020), preventing stakeholders to **critically understand** how their interactions with data affect their lives & to **critically use** data for personal and societal benefit (Pangrazio & Selwyn, 2023). This lack of **critical data literacy** risks reinforcing dominant systems of power, privilege, and oppression (Collins, 1990) which further marginalises already disadvantaged communities (Barad, 2007).

By applying the construction process of data physicalisation to reveal the entanglements between power and data, this research aims to support the critical skills of understanding and applying data in a personal & societal context.

LinkedIn

Publications

Main outcomes

- SQ1. A participatory method that reveals and balances power dynamics in participatory data practices (*in progress*).
- SQ2. A model that explains how stakeholders develop critical data literacy skills by physically engaging with data (*under revision*).
- SQ3. A cross-disciplinary ontology that facilitates the analysis of power dynamics embedded in participatory data physicalisation as a data practice (*published in CHI'25*).

Research questions

How can the construction process of data physicalisation reveal the entanglements between power and data?

- SQ1. What are the entanglements between power and data during the infrastructuring process of data?
- SQ2. How can the construction process of data physicalisation reveal these entanglements?
- SQ3. What are the entanglements of data physicalisation as an infrastructuring process itself?

Main Outlook/Recommendations

To design HDI that supports critical literacy skills by revealing the power dynamics embedded in data, designers should reflect upon the decisions during planning, participation and dissemination about:

- *How are complex issues represented so that they reflect stakeholders and communities' interests?*
- *How is data contextualised into individual meanings?*
- *How can participants express continuous consent throughout their engagement with data?*

SQ1. Using a data physicalisation method to negotiate with other stakeholders in a data practice.

SQ3. By applying a cross-disciplinary ontology onto a corpus of data physicalisation artefacts, we reveal the power dynamics involved in their planning, construction and dissemination.

SQ2. We modelled how a game-based physicalisation tool supported stakeholders to discuss, negotiate and reflect about their shared data infrastructure, which allowed them to build critical data literacy skills.

ODECO

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

Enhancing Open Data Ecosystem using AI and CI

Towards a FAIR Open Data Ecosystem

Umair Ahmed (University of Camerino)

Umair.ahmed@unicam.it

Research questions

- Are LLMs effective methodologies for enhancing FAIRness in OD Ecosystem:
 - Metadata Generation
 - Semantic Search
 - Interoperable LD vocabularies
- How can CI enhance open-data FAIRness via metadata, dataset cleaning, & versioning?

Methodology

- Dataset \Rightarrow Descriptions \Rightarrow Themes, Keywords \Rightarrow Embeddings \Rightarrow Semantic Search (**Fig 1**)
- Metadata: Finetune LLMs, Eval (Rouge, Cosine, 1to1, Emb) (**Fig 3**)
- Linked Data Semantic Search: LLM \Rightarrow SPARQL \Rightarrow Embedding \Rightarrow Rerank \Rightarrow Results (**Fig 2**)

Results

- Metadata Extraction:
 - Keywords: Llama-3.2 (**81%**)
 - Themes: T5Large (**77%**)
 - Description: DeepSeek-R1 (85%)
- Semantic Search (ScholarKG):
 - QueryType: Roberta (**99%**)
 - Search: GPT + SPARQL + Embeddings (**96%**)
- Search(EDP): Embeddings(**363938**)

Fig 1: Enhancing Metadata and Semantic Search using AI and CI

Fig 2: Semantic Search using LLMs and Embeddings

Fig 3a: Description Generation

Fig 3b: Theme Extraction

Fig 3c: Keyword Extraction

Fig 3: Automated Metadata Extraction using LLMs

ODECO

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

Technical aspects for Inclusiveness across user domains in Open Data Portals

Abdul Aziz (Universidad de Zaragoza)
abdul.aziz@unizar.es

Objective

Investigate methodologies for the inclusiveness in open data portals to enhance accessibility and the user interaction with open data portals.

- On the one hand, open data portals should facilitate an easy discovery of the resources of interest to the different user domains.
- On the other hand, open data portals should facilitate the interaction with users if the discovered resources or facilities do not comply with their needs.

Research questions

1. Is it possible to adopt a supplier-driven approach for inclusiveness?
2. Can we improve the inclusiveness since the design of the backend through a proper curation and annotation of datasets?
3. Is it possible to adopt a user-driven approach for inclusiveness?
4. How can we transform users into the main actors of open data ecosystems?

Main outcomes

1. **A supplier-driven approach for inclusiveness:** A framework for the thematic annotation of open government data. The framework provides and compares the performance of different machine learning classification techniques considering both annotated and not annotated metadata corpora.
2. **A user-driven approach for inclusiveness:** A conceptual definition of roundtrip feedback in open data portals. We provide design guidelines to bridge stakeholder needs, improve data quality, and strengthen user engagement.
3. **A method for the analysis of feedback through social networks:** This method allows us to compare the evolution and maturity of user engagement through social networks in different Open Data initiatives.

Enhancing Open Government Data Through User Engagement, Annotation, and Feedback Mechanisms

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

Open data usage in elementary school

Learning designs and open data competencies

Alejandra Celis Vargas (Aalborg University)

cacv@ikp.aau.dk

Background

The lack of skills of citizens has been identified as one of the main barriers for achieving the benefits of open data. Although the development of open data competencies in school is essential for the engagement of lay audiences and young citizens in open data ecosystems, its definition and learning designs are lacking.

Research questions

How can educational designs foster competencies in young school students to engage in open data ecosystems and address real-world challenges using open data?
What are open data competencies and the learning designs to develop them?

Main theoretical outcomes

1. Open data competencies are authentic open data inquiry to foster Data Literacy and Real-world problem solving.
2. Authentic and game-oriented learning designs principles.

Methodological framework

Design-based research focuses on theoretical and practical outcomes.
3 Cycles and 5 Interventions
117 students (14 to 16 years), 9 teachers in Danish schools (7th to 9th grade)

Main practical outcomes

The Open Data Newsroom is a role-playing game that immerse young students into a data journalism practice to unravel an environmental local mystery with data.

1. Local real-world problems
2. Personally relevant for the students
3. Authentic open data practice

ODECO

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

Decoding Open Data Intermediation Business Models

More than Just a Bridge

Ashraf Shaharudin (Delft University of Technology)
a.a.binahmadshaharudin@tudelft.nl

Background

Open data intermediaries (ODIs) were regarded as key to addressing challenges in open data ecosystems (ODE) and optimising values from open data. However, in-depth knowledge regarding their business models was lacking. Such deficiency limited the understanding of the conditions that may steer ODIs towards supporting sustainable ODEs.

Research questions

1. What are ODIs?
2. What are the potential contributions of ODIs in ODEs?
3. What are the common archetypes of ODIs' business models?
4. What aspects should be considered in developing ODI business models that support sustainable ODE?

Main outcomes

1. ODIs are not just a 'bridge' between open data providers and end-users, but they intermediate resource flows and relationship building between various open data actors, including other open data intermediaries.
2. ODIs' business models do not have to rely on generating revenue from open data products/services, as the open data intermediation can simply serve as a supporting factor to the revenue-generating products/services.
3. Having a vested interest in the open data intermediation business model, through tangible investment and expected own benefits, is an important factor for its durability and longevity.
4. ODIs do not have to be a formally or legally structured and recognised entity, but can also be a fluid 'community of communities'.

Sydney, Australia in OSM in December 2006 and October 2010

OSM technical infrastructure to contribute and use data

ODECO

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

Open data meets data justice

Understanding how to govern open data equitably

Caterina Santoro (KU Leuven)

Email: caterina.santoro@kuleuven.be

Problem definition

Epistemic injustice of knowledge production
Commodification of data
Lack of capabilities
Financial constraints
Governance 'on us, without us'

We ask

How can we govern open data **equitably**?

(in theory and practice)

Main outcomes, connecting concepts, and devising solutions

My research in

- (1) Systematic Literature Review
- (2) Conceptual paper
- (3) In-depth case studies: one on the governance of **equality data**, and one on the simultaneous implementation of the **Open Data Directive** and the **Data Governance Act**
- (4) White paper on the just implementation of the **EU public sector data regulations**

Conclusion

Empowering all social actors through open data requires considering the governance of administrative data creation and how public institutions implement regulations on public sector data sharing.

Even more relevant now

There is a political economy to open data, which is not neutral, and it is now at the center of further debate (e.g., the Trump Administration, new EU data strategy).

ODECO

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.

Annex 4 – Practical recommendations

Recommendations for Sustainable Open Data Ecosystems

Ramya Chandrasekhar and Melanie Dulong de Rosnay & the ODECO consortium

Background

Open data are crucial for scientific knowledge production, transparency and accountability, as well as innovation. The value of open data is multi-faceted, and include social as well as economic value. This includes the creation of new open datasets (often by combining or adding to existing open datasets), identifying social issues of concern, creating new technological infrastructures for open data, offering educational and awareness activities related to open data, and new data-driven products and services. However, open data initiatives and infrastructures also face many challenges ranging from lack of financial support to limited participation of non-government data holders, which impact their sustainability.

The following set of recommendations is meant to support the future of open data, by imagining, building and maintaining open data ecosystems that are financially, socially and ecologically sustainable, equitable, and empower all stakeholders.

Data quality

1. Discoverability
Multiple access modalities;
machine-readable formats

2. Metadata
Comprehensive metadata; use
of AI for metadata generation

3. Engagement and participation
A priori, ongoing and a posteriori
strategies to involve all actors

Wide re-use

4. Beyond open government data
Legal instruments, financial incentives
and governance strategies for open
data from non-government actors

5. Data literacy
Leverage education sector for
data skills and data literacy

6. Mind the gap(s)
Power dynamics in terms of who
and what is "missed out" in open
data initiatives

Infrastructures

7. Usability
User experience matters

8. Interoperability
Uptake of interoperability standards is crucial

9. Public administrations' investments
Funding, infrastructures and coordinating function of public administrations

ODECO

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955569.